

Role of science and scientists in public environmental policy debates: the case of EU agrochemical and nature restoration regulations

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1

2 **Abstract**

3 1) Halting biodiversity loss, mitigating global warming, and maintaining the long-term
4 viability of rural and urban areas requires urgent policy action. However, environmental
5 policies often trigger resistance and highly polarised public debates, with some actors
6 employing pseudo-scientific claims. This raises concern about the increasing impact
7 of misinformation on policy-making.

8 2) Here, we analyse the role of science and scientists in the public debate around two
9 pieces of legislation that were proposed in 2022 by the European Commission as part
10 of the Green Deal, namely the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) and the
11 Sustainable Use Regulation of plant protection products (SUR).

12 3) First, we examine key claims against these two legislative proposals, and contrast
13 them with scientific evidence. We show that these claims fail to consider ample
14 scientific evidence that restoring nature and reducing the use of agrochemicals are
15 essential for maintaining long-term agricultural production and enhancing food
16 security. Critics further failed to acknowledge that the NRR and SUR may generate
17 new employment opportunities and stimulate innovation, with high return rates and
18 multiple beneficiaries across society, fostering a transition to sustainable production
19 and consumption models.

20 4) Second, we examine how the publication of an open letter, signed by 6,000 scientists,
21 may have influenced the public debate. We contrast the role that scientific evidence
22 played in the fate of the NRR, which was adopted, against the fate of the SUR, which
23 was rejected by the European Parliament.

24 5) We draw lessons from these two cases that illustrate the global tension between
25 environmental protection and economic-driven interests to spread misinformation. We
26 argue that scientists should play an important role in making scientific evidence more
27 accessible and available to the general public and policymakers for informed decision

28 making. We recommend that scientists be proactive and unbiased in providing
29 information and data, and that policymakers use scientific evidence and engage
30 scientists in developing much needed, well informed environmental policies.

31

32 **Zusammenfassung**

33 1) Um den Verlust der Biodiversität aufzuhalten, den Klimawandel zu bremsen und die
34 langfristige Nachhaltigkeit von ländlichen und städtischen Gebieten zu erhalten, sind dringend
35 politische Maßnahmen erforderlich. Umweltpolitische Maßnahmen lösen jedoch häufig
36 Widerstand und stark polarisierte öffentliche Debatten aus, wobei einige Akteure
37 pseudowissenschaftliche Behauptungen aufstellen. Dies gibt Anlass zur Besorgnis über den
38 zunehmenden Einfluss von Fehlinformationen auf die Politikgestaltung.

39 2) Hier analysieren wir die Rolle von Wissenschaft und Forschenden in der öffentlichen
40 Debatte über zwei Rechtsvorschriften, die 2022 von der Europäischen Kommission als Teil
41 des Green Deal vorgeschlagen wurden, nämlich die Verordnung zur Wiederherstellung der
42 Natur (NRR) und die Verordnung zur nachhaltigen Verwendung von Pflanzenschutzmitteln
43 (SUR).

44 3) Zunächst untersuchen wir die wichtigsten Behauptungen gegen diese beiden
45 vorgeschlagenen Politikinstrumente und stellen sie wissenschaftlichen Erkenntnissen
46 gegenüber. Wir zeigen, dass diese Behauptungen die umfangreiche wissenschaftliche
47 Evidenz außer Acht lassen, dass die Wiederherstellung der Natur und die Verringerung des
48 Einsatzes von Agrochemikalien für die Aufrechterhaltung einer langfristigen
49 landwirtschaftlichen Produktion und für die Verbesserung der Ernährungssicherheit
50 unerlässlich sind. Die Kritiker verkennen auch, dass die NRR und der SUR neue
51 Beschäftigungsmöglichkeiten schaffen und Innovationen anregen können, mit hohen

52 Renditen und zahlreichen Nutznießenden in der Gesellschaft, die den Übergang zu
53 nachhaltigen Produktions- und Konsummodellen fördern können.

54 4) Zweitens untersuchen wir, wie die Veröffentlichung eines offenen Briefes, der von 6.000
55 Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftlern unterzeichnet wurde, die öffentliche Debatte
56 beeinflusst haben könnte. Wir vergleichen die Rolle, die wissenschaftliche Erkenntnisse bei
57 der Verabschiedung des NRR gespielt haben, mit dem Schicksal des SUR, welches vom
58 Europäischen Parlament abgelehnt wurde.

59 5) Diesen beiden Fällen verdeutlichen das globale Spannungsverhältnis zwischen
60 Umweltschutz und wirtschaftlich motivierten Interessen zur Verbreitung von
61 Fehlinformationen. Wir empfehlen, dass Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler eine
62 wichtige Rolle dabei spielen sollten, der Öffentlichkeit und den politischen
63 Entscheidungsträgern wissenschaftliche Erkenntnisse für eine fundierte
64 Entscheidungsfindung zugänglicher und verfügbarer zu machen. Forschende sollten proaktiv
65 und unparteiisch Informationen und Daten zur Verfügung stellen, und dass politischen
66 Entscheidungsträger sollten wissenschaftliche Erkenntnisse nutzen und
67 Wissenschaftlerinnen und Wissenschaftler in die Entwicklung dringend benötigter, Evidenz-
68 basierter Umweltpolitik einbeziehen.

69

70 **Resumen**

71 1) Detener la pérdida de biodiversidad, mitigar el calentamiento global y mantener la
72 viabilidad a largo plazo de las zonas rurales y urbanas exige una actuación política urgente.
73 Sin embargo, las políticas medioambientales a menudo generan resistencia y debates
74 públicos muy polarizados, en los que algunos actores emplean afirmaciones
75 pseudocientíficas. Esto suscita preocupación por el creciente impacto de la desinformación
76 en la elaboración de políticas.

77 2) Aquí analizamos el papel de la ciencia y los científicos en el debate público en torno a
78 dos propuestas legislativas presentadas en 2022 por la Comisión Europea como parte del
79 Pacto Verde- el Reglamento de Restauración de la Naturaleza (RNR) y el Reglamento de
80 Uso Sostenible de Productos Fitosanitarios (SUR).

81 3) En primer lugar, examinamos las principales alegaciones contra estas dos propuestas
82 legislativas y las contrastamos con evidencias científicas. Demostramos que estas
83 afirmaciones no tienen en cuenta la amplia evidencia científica de que restaurar la
84 naturaleza y reducir el uso de productos agroquímicos son esenciales para mantener la
85 producción agrícola a largo plazo y mejorar la seguridad alimentaria. Los críticos tampoco
86 reconocen que la RNR y la SUR pueden generar nuevas oportunidades de empleo y
87 estimular la innovación, con altas tasas de retorno y múltiples beneficiarios en toda la
88 sociedad, fomentando así una transición hacia modelos sostenibles de producción y
89 consumo.

90 4) En segundo lugar, examinamos cómo la publicación de una carta abierta, firmada por
91 6.000 científicos, pudo haber influido en el debate público. Contrastamos el papel que jugó
92 la evidencia científica en el destino de la NRR, que fue adoptada, frente al destino del SUR,
93 que fue rechazado por el Parlamento Europeo.

94 5) Extraemos lecciones de estos dos casos que ilustran la tensión global entre la protección
95 del medio ambiente y los intereses económicos que impulsan la desinformación. Defendemos
96 que los científicos deben desempeñar un papel importante y hacer que la evidencia científica
97 sea más accesible y esté disponible tanto para el público en general como para los
98 responsables políticos, con el fin de que tomen decisiones informadas. Recomendamos que
99 los científicos sean proactivos e imparciales a la hora de proporcionar información y datos, y
100 que los responsables políticos utilicen la evidencia científica e involucren a los científicos en
101 el desarrollo de las políticas medioambientales bien informadas, que tan necesarias son.

102 Introduction

103 We are currently facing a combination of global crises, many of which are directly generated
104 by anthropogenic pressures on the Earth's systems. Having already surpassed six out of nine
105 Planetary Boundaries (Persson et al., 2022; Richardson et al. 2023; Rockström et al., 2009),
106 urgent action is needed to find sustainable paths forward for society. Halting biodiversity loss
107 and mitigating climate change, while maintaining long-term productivity of ecosystems used
108 for food provision, require us to reduce the human pressures driving current crises and restore
109 nature's capacity to recover and deliver life-support services.

110 Pressures to intensify the use of land and sea are still growing. Infrastructure
111 development, land-use change, and habitat degradation are continuing throughout the world,
112 and biodiversity losses are accelerating (IPBES 2019). While various policies and regulations
113 globally are being negotiated and introduced, many of them are weakly designed or poorly
114 implemented (e.g. protected areas and restoring nature; Bekessy et al., 2010; Gill et al., 2017).
115 In other cases, existing policies are being deregulated (Ruggiero et al, 2021; Gasparri et al,
116 2015). Policy processes around the world are being hijacked to pursue political or economic
117 goals, sometimes in the name of science but often using pseudo-scientific claims. For
118 example, Samet & Burke (2020) document how the US has deregulated pollution control by
119 reducing the Environmental Protection Agency's research capacity, and altering long-
120 established scientific protocols. As of 2025, scientific data are being removed from numerous
121 official US government websites, including epidemiological information, weather, climate, and
122 human population demographics (Gafney 2025; Wikipedia 2025).

123

124 Scientists across disciplines are concerned that public debates and policy processes
125 at all levels are being increasingly polarised and potentially disrupted by misinformation (Yang
126 et al., 2017). In particular, social media effectively spread misinformation as they selectively
127 circulate contents beyond their original source context (Gundersen et al., 2022) - a problem

128 which is well known in the context of climate change (Farrell et al., 2019) and was highly
129 evident in the case of COVID19 (Hartley & Vu, 2020). This particularly causes problems in
130 times when numerous new targets for national and international environmental policies are
131 being set and ratified (e.g. Kunming-Montreal Biodiversity Framework (Convention on
132 Biological Diversity 2022)). Measures to protect the environment are often viewed as barriers
133 to meeting other human needs and interests, such as infrastructure development, food
134 security, or economic growth (Samet & Burke, 2020). Since failures to protect the environment
135 have documented long-term costs for society (Ackerman & Stanton, 2008), it becomes urgent
136 to consider how scientific evidence could be operationalized better to support decision-making
137 processes (Cook et al., 2013; Langer et al., 2016). Public debates usually occur over relatively
138 short periods of time and as a result, scientists who wish to weigh in on the debate need to
139 provide a rapid synthesis of unbiased expert opinions based on the best available evidence,
140 while maintaining a reliable representation of complexities and uncertainties. Thus, the
141 process of debunking misinformation may require proactive intervention in decision-making
142 processes, without violating the role of an honest broker (Pielke, 2007).

143 Here, we focus on two policies recently proposed in the EU under the EU Green Deal
144 framework, the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) and the Sustainable Use Regulation
145 (SUR), as two contrasting case studies. First, we examine eight dominant arguments that were
146 made against the NRR and SUR (Table 1 and Supporting Information Table S1), and compare
147 these claims with scientific evidence. We then discuss the role scientists played in the public
148 debates around these negotiations. Finally, we reflect on the role of science and scientists in
149 contributing to evidence-based policies, using the best available science, in highly political or
150 contested circumstances.

151

152 **The Nature Restoration Law (NRR) and the Sustainable Use Regulation of plant**
153 **protection products (SUR)**

154 These two legal proposals responded to the poor state of the environment in the EU. Eighty-
155 one percent of so-called 'Sites of Community Importance' that are presumably protected, are
156 in unfavourable or poor condition (European Environment Agency, 2020). The majority of soils
157 in Europe (60-70%) are classified as degraded (Veerman et al., 2020). Nearly 70% of the fish
158 stocks are subject to overfishing and over half of these are outside of safe biological limits
159 (Froese et al., 2018). Pesticides are detected above thresholds of concern in 83% of
160 agricultural soils (Silva et al., 2019) and in 22% of aquatic monitoring sites (EEA, 2023), as
161 well as in 84% of urine tests among Europeans (Ottenbros et al., 2023). These examples
162 illustrate an overall environmental crisis, impacting our health and wellbeing.

163 The European Green Deal, as originally proposed by the European Commission
164 (2019) attempted to respond to this crisis by providing an ambitious long-term strategy to
165 protect and enhance the EU's natural capital. The Green Deal aims to (i) preserve and restore
166 ecosystems and biodiversity, as reflected in the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European
167 Commission, 2020a); (ii) develop a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system,
168 represented in the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020b); and (iii) reach zero
169 pollution and a toxic-free environment (European Commission, 2021). To achieve the Green
170 Deal objectives, the European Commission proposed several new policies, including the NRR
171 and SUR.

172 The Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR, a.k.a. Nature Restoration Law; European
173 Commission, 2022a) aims to establish effective restoration measures on habitats protected
174 under the Habitats Directive that are not in good condition (40%, 60% and 90% by 2030, 2040
175 and 2050, respectively) and sets targets to ensure the resilience of agrifood systems. It
176 includes quantitative targets, timelines, wide geographical coverage and implementation
177 details to track progress, and it addresses some key weaknesses of the present policy
178 framework, which is based on voluntary measures (Hering et al. 2023). The NRR can therefore
179 be considered a global landmark as a legally binding instrument to implement the Global
180 Biodiversity Framework across borders, i.e., across all EU member states.

181 The Sustainable Use Regulation of Plant Protection Products (a.k.a Sustainable Use
182 Regulation or SUR; European Commission, 2022b), primarily aimed to reduce the overall use
183 and risk from chemical pesticides by 50%, and to reduce the use of hazardous pesticides by
184 50% at the EU level. Other objectives of the SUR proposal were to (i) increase the application
185 and enforcement of integrated pest management and the use of less hazardous and non-
186 chemical alternatives to chemical pesticides, (ii) improve the availability of monitoring data on
187 pesticides, health and environment, (iii) enhance the implementation, application and
188 enforcement of legal provisions across Member States to improve policy effectiveness and
189 efficiency, and (iv) promote the adoption of new technologies toward these goals. The SUR
190 would have required Member States to adopt and implement national targets toward 2030,
191 compared to 2015-2017 as baseline years. However, these targets were not legally binding
192 and lacked specific enforcement mechanisms.

193 The Green Deal has faced growing resistance, culminating in an intense political
194 campaign against the NRR and the SUR during 2023 (Euronews 2023). Various societal
195 actors and policymakers argued that the NRR and SUR would impede the swift recovery of
196 European economies from such crises as Covid19 and the war in Ukraine. Claims were made
197 that the NRR and SUR would have adverse effects on farmers, fishers, and society at large,
198 threatening food security, reducing jobs and competing with the transition to renewable energy
199 (Table S1). Despite the somewhat similar claims against both, the two policies had different
200 fates. The NRR was negotiated among Parliament Members from June to November 2023.
201 After its final version was voted favourably in November 2023, it passed final approval by the
202 European Council in June 2024. The SUR was rejected by the European Parliament in
203 November 2023.

204

205 **Key claims against the NRR and SUR and their scientific** 206 **analysis**

207 Here we analyse eight key claims used in the campaigns against the NRR and SUR
208 (Table 1, concrete examples in Table S1), and compare them with scientific evidence
209 gathered by our multidisciplinary expert group.

210

211 **1. Land taken out of production**

212 A key claim against the NRR and SUR was that they would result in farmland being
213 abandoned or taken out of production, thereby leading to significant declines in
214 agricultural production. This claim was primarily based on the fact that the NRR initially
215 proposed that at least 10% of the EU's agricultural area should be covered with high-
216 diversity landscape features (Article 14 in European Commission 2022a). Taking 10%
217 of agricultural land out of production would obviously be a valid concern for farmers
218 (Wachter-Karpfinger & Wyrzens, 2024), especially in times of increasing demand for
219 global food supply (European Commission, 2022e).

220 However, the claim that the NRR would take 10% of agricultural land out of
221 production is erroneous. First, during the early stages of the NRR's negotiations, "high-
222 diversity landscape features" were redefined in a way that allowed some level of
223 productive activities, and in its final version, the 10% target was removed. Instead, the
224 NRR focused on improving the state of habitat types in the Habitats Directive, including
225 several grassland types that depend on the maintenance of extensive farming
226 practices. Moreover, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in its current funding
227 period (2023-2027), already requires farmers to dedicate the equivalent of at least 3%

228 of arable land to biodiversity and non-productive elements, with a possibility of
229 receiving support via eco-schemes to reach a 7% target.

230 Secondly, unrelated to nature restoration efforts, some farmland areas are
231 already gradually falling out of production in the EU. Land abandonment occurs in
232 marginalised regions where regional socio-economic viability is undermined (Alliance
233 Environment, 2020). This is particularly true for so-called “High Nature Value”
234 farmlands, where CAP support is insufficient to prevent the abandonment of the least
235 productive land (Scown et al., 2020; Pe’er et al., 2021).

236 Finally, the 10% claim does not affect farmers directly: the targets are set for
237 Member States, who are flexible on how they set their own national targets, while
238 farmers can contribute to this target on a voluntary basis. Importantly, this approach
239 can allow for restoring agricultural habitats associated with low productivity levels,
240 such as peatlands or areas with persistent or forecasted waterlogging and flooding
241 (Bonn et al., 2016; Tanneberger et al., 2021).

242

243 **2. Yield losses**

244 Another claim asserted that the NRR and SUR would result in yield losses, and
245 therefore a decrease in agricultural production. This was based on the assumption that
246 the SUR would result in a full 50% reduction in pesticide use (Article 4 in European
247 Commission 2022a) in all crops and all EU Member States. Several studies analysed
248 the potential impacts of such pesticide reduction on crop yields and concluded that it
249 would indeed reduce crop yields – up to 30% in worst-case scenarios, leading to higher
250 food prices, increased imports and reduced exports of commodities (Beckman et al.,
251 2020). Such impacts would indeed be worrying.

252 However, these studies were based on a simplistic interpretation of how
253 pesticide reduction targets could be implemented, and what their impacts are likely to
254 be (Schneider et al., 2023). Typically, pesticide reduction is not implemented in
255 isolation but rather associated with other practices such as precision agriculture or
256 integrated pest management. Accordingly, studies indicated that pesticide use can be
257 reduced by more than 40% without negative effects on food productivity (Lechenet et
258 al., 2017). This can be achieved by agroecological management practices, such as
259 implementing diversified crop rotation (Deguine et al., 2021; Lechenet et al, 2014) or
260 using cover crops (Wezel et al, 2014). In addition, precision agriculture approaches,
261 such as autonomous weeding robots equipped with specific spectral sensors,
262 combined with online information systems on pest population development, can
263 reduce the application of pesticides considerably (Anastasiou et al, 2023; Finger,
264 2023; Rajmis et al., 2022).

265 Furthermore, those studies estimating that the SUR would reduce crop yields
266 failed to consider the positive feedback that pesticide reduction would have on yields.
267 Biodiversity loss and associated losses of ecosystem services (Beckmann et al., 2019;
268 IPBES, 2018) are among the main drivers of yield losses, in particular under climate
269 change (Seppelt et al., 2020). Fifty percent of the EU area planted with pollinator-
270 dependent crops experiences yield losses due to a deficit in pollinators (European
271 Commission, 2022d), creating an economic loss equivalent to 8.1–9.9% of the total
272 value of plant production in the EU (FAO, 2023). Yield losses due to droughts in 2018
273 ranged between 15 and 25% in many German arable systems (D'Agostino, 2018),
274 with an estimated loss valued at around €7-8 bn. (Trenczek et al., 2022). Further, yield
275 losses are affected by poor soil conditions in more than 60% of the EU area, due to
276 reduced soil biodiversity, pollution, loss of organic matter, compaction, salinization,

277 and soil sealing (Veerman et al., 2020; JRC, 2023). Finally, climate change increases
278 the severity of pest infestations (Lenton et al., 2019; Harvey et al., 2023). A recent
279 study linked the die-off of bats due to an invasive fungal pathogen in the Eastern USA
280 with an increase of 31.3% in pesticide use to substitute losses in natural pest control
281 by bats. This resulted in an increase of 7.9% in infant death rates in the affected
282 counties, while crop revenue nevertheless declined by 28.9% (Frank, 2024).

283 The measures proposed by the two regulations could help reduce long-term risks of
284 yield loss by increasing functional diversity, which can help alleviate the adverse
285 effects of climate change on crop production (Dainese et al., 2019 and references
286 therein). This can be achieved through implementing agroecological practices, such
287 as maintaining semi-natural landscape features (e.g., Petit & Landis, 2023),
288 diversifying crops, reducing field sizes, employing soil protection and restoration
289 measures, and implementing agroforestry (Reganold & Wachter, 2016).

290

291 **3. Food insecurity**

292 A third claim asserted that by taking land out of production and hampering
293 yields, the NRR and SUR would increase global food insecurity. This claim rested on
294 the EU's central role in world markets. Some studies have estimated that the Farm to
295 Fork and biodiversity strategies may result in increased food insecurity for an
296 additional 30.1 million (EU-only) to 171 million (Global) people in 2030 (e.g.
297 Baquedano et al., 2022).

298 However, these studies insufficiently consider that in the EU food production is
299 not a key determinant of food security. Rather, food accessibility, food waste and high

300 consumption of meat in industrial countries have been shown to be as important, if not
301 more important, than global food production (Holt-Giménez et al., 2012; FAO et al.
302 2021; Tschamntke et al., 2012). Notably, the EU primarily exports dairy and meat
303 products (European Commission, 2023). For instance, between 2010 and 2020, the
304 EU produced more than its own requirements for products such as pork (117%), beef
305 and veal (106%), poultry (111%) and milk (110%) (EU Commission, 2023). In addition,
306 most of the grain produced in the EU is used to produce animal feed (62.4% in
307 2020/21; European Commission 2020; Lakner, 2023) and an increasing land demand
308 for biofuel production. This leads to increased food prices, making foods less
309 accessible to the poorest in society (Lakner, 2023). Finally, the EU heavily depends
310 upon imports of many products including soy (mostly for feed), palm oil, oil seeds and
311 maize, leading to substantial use of land and resources in the global south for feed
312 and industrial crops (European Commission 2023; Zinngrebe et al. 2024).

313 Consequently, the most efficient way for the EU to contribute to both local and
314 global food security is to reduce the production and consumption of meat and dairy
315 products (Costa et al., 2022), to reduce food waste (Parfitt et al., 2010; Shepon et al.,
316 2018), and biofuel production (Lakner et al. 2022). In Germany alone, approximately
317 12 million tonnes of food are wasted annually, of which 7 – 7.6 million tonnes are
318 avoidable (Schmidt et al., 2019). A European legislative framework for sustainable
319 food systems (FSFS), that was originally due for publication in autumn 2023, would
320 have been key to achieve this transformation of food consumption patterns. The
321 combination of the FSFS, the NRR and SUR could have therefore contributed to
322 reaching environmental objectives without jeopardising food production, let alone food
323 security (Röös et al., 2022).

324 Some misleading arguments were carried into the final formulation of the NRR.
325 For example, Article 27 of the NRR requires the Commission to suspend its
326 implementation in agricultural areas under emergency situations “*with severe Union-*
327 *wide consequences for the availability of land required to secure sufficient agricultural*
328 *production for Union food consumption*”. With only 30% of agricultural land in Europe
329 used to food crops, we cannot foresee justifiable conditions for this to occur. If real
330 food shortages were to occur, it would be more effective to transition the vast land
331 tracts that are currently used for feed and fuel production to produce food crops, rather
332 than convert the use of fallow and marginal lands - with marginal benefits but high
333 risks.

334

335 **4. Fishing restrictions**

336 A fourth claim asserted that the NRR would have a negative impact on fisheries
337 due to limitations and changes in fishing areas. This claim was based on the fact that
338 NRR restrictions, within strictly protected Marine Protected Areas (MPAs, Article 5),
339 may cause a “displacement effect” where some fisheries lose access to certain areas.
340 Such displacements occur especially during so-called transition periods, namely in
341 response to new management measures (Suuronen et al., 2010; Vaughan, 2017).

342 However, this claim failed to consider that the main risks to fisheries originate
343 from the combination of unsustainable fisheries, climate change and pollution
344 (Moerlein and Carothers, 2012; Portner and Knust, 2007). The fraction of marine fish
345 stocks harvested at an unsustainable level globally has increased from 10% in the
346 1970s to almost 35% in 2017 (Stankus, 2021), and reaches 70% in some parts of
347 Europe (Issifu et al., 2022). Large species, either directly targeted or caught as
348 bycatch, are under exceptionally high risk of extinction (Fernandes et al., 2017).

349 Moreover, no-take zones (i.e. the strictest protection level) cover merely 1% of the
350 area of European MPAs, therefore having a direct effect on a marginal proportion of
351 fisheries – and even when affected, losses can be compensated (Greenstreet et al.,
352 2009; Suuronen et al., 2010).

353 In contrast, establishing MPAs, especially large and fully protected ones, has
354 been shown to be a cost-effective means to preserve and even enhance fisheries
355 yields (Di Lorenzo et al., 2020; Frid et al., 2023; Pendleton et al., 2018; Sala &
356 Giakoumi, 2018). MPAs can lead to an increase in species biomass and diversity, and
357 promote the dispersal of larvae and adults of various taxa (Pendleton et al., 2018 and
358 references therein). For example, a meta-analysis has shown that the biomass of
359 whole fish assemblages in fully protected marine reserves is, on average, 570%
360 greater than in unprotected areas (Sala & Giakoumi, 2018). This increase may benefit
361 adjacent fisheries due to spillover effects from MPAs into nearby less protected or
362 unprotected areas (Di Lorenzo et al., 2020; Edgar et al., 2014; Grorud-Colvert et al.,
363 2021). For instance, fish abundance is 30% higher and biomass is 50% higher along
364 the MPA borders compared to more distant regions (Di Lorenzo et al., 2020). Finally,
365 the positive effects of MPAs are likely to persist also under climate change (Frid et al.,
366 2023), thereby mitigating the impacts of the possibly-biggest challenge that
367 commercial fisheries will face in the future (Pendleton et al., 2018).

368 “High-risk” fishing practices currently take place in over 80% of the total area of
369 MPAs in Europe and the UK (Perry et al., 2022). For example, bottom trawling,
370 considered as especially destructive for marine flora and fauna (Steadman, 2021),
371 harmful in terms of greenhouse gas emissions and contested in terms of
372 socioeconomic impacts (Steadman et al., 2021), has been documented in almost 60%

373 of Atlantic and Baltic Sea MPAs (Dureuil et al., 2018). By improving the protection of
374 few marine areas, the NRR can therefore contribute to the restoration of key nurseries
375 or essential fish habitats, such as seagrass and macroalgal beds and other coastal
376 habitats, which will help the recovery of fish and shellfish, and in return benefit
377 fisheries.

378

379 **5. Income and job security**

380 Another claim was that the NRR and SUR would “kill jobs”. Job security is indeed an
381 important issue, since employment in agriculture and fisheries has continuously
382 declined during the last decades. Between 2005 and 2020 alone, the number of farms
383 in the EU declined by 37%, to 9.1 in 2020 (i.e., 5.3 million fewer than in 2005; Eurostat,
384 2022). Some assessments of the potential impacts of the Farm to Fork strategy did
385 forecast losses of incomes and jobs (e.g. Barreiro et al., 2021; Beckman et al., 2020;
386 Henning et al., 2021). These assessments, however, have been criticised due to their
387 conceptual and practical limitations (Candel, 2022). For instance, they ignored the
388 socio-economic and technological adaptation capacities of farms, they ignored
389 interactions between complementary policy instruments, and did not consider the
390 entire value chain. Yet more importantly, they ignored the key factors affecting jobs in
391 agriculture and fisheries, namely, structural changes (i.e., increasing centralization)
392 and technical progress resulting in the replacement of labour by technologies
393 (Westhoek et al., 2014). Current agricultural policies have also disadvantaged small-
394 scale farmers and failed to avert the ongoing rural exodus (Scown et al., 2020).
395 Likewise the replacement of labour by technologies has resulted in a rapid loss of jobs
396 in the fisheries sector (Gascuel et al., 2011). Finally, the effects of climate change and
397 land degradation further make farming less attractive livelihood (Buchenrieder, 2007).

398 Highlighting job losses while ignoring both the drivers of unemployment and the
399 potential for job-creation is, at best, misleading. Efficient ways to ensure job security
400 in the agricultural and fisheries sectors would be to improve the resilience of small-
401 and family-businesses, improve the distribution of existing subsidies, promote
402 sustainable production, and generate greater benefits by shortening value chains
403 (e.g., direct marketing), in line with agroecological principles. By restoring ecosystems
404 and their multiple uses, the NRR could contribute to more sustainable production while
405 bearing the potential to create new employment, through new production models (e.g.
406 paludiculture; Temmink et al., 2023). For instance, business models focusing on
407 extensification tend to be more labour intensive and therefore preserve or generate
408 employment opportunities (Vandeplas et al., 2022; Vona, 2019). Most importantly, by
409 complementing the Nature Directives, the measures proposed by both the NRR and
410 SUR could prevent the climate-change-induced collapse of local and regional
411 production systems and, with them, the subsequent collapse of jobs in the coming
412 decades. This, however, will largely depend on implementation, and particularly, the
413 efforts made by Member States in mobilising additional funding (see also Hering et al.
414 2023).

415

416 **6. Burden on society**

417 Another claim was that the NRR and SUR would generate new restrictions that would
418 increase the burden on society, in a period of crises when people cannot bear
419 additional burdens. Setting new requirements or regulations to restore nature, and
420 developing alternatives to pesticides, does indeed require significant funding and
421 investment. There can also be short-term local scale trade-offs between production

422 and nature-conservation measures, generating both winners and losers (e.g. farmers,
423 fisheries or real-estate investors affected).

424 In the long term and on much larger scales, however, society pays twice for the
425 unsustainable way in which we use land- and sea-scapes, and particularly farmlands.
426 On the one hand, public funds are used to support farmers through the CAP, with an
427 investment of €55 bn./year. On the other hand, unsustainable land-uses contribute to
428 climate change, biodiversity losses, soil degradation, and reduction in water availability
429 and quality, while enhancing risks e.g. from floods - while calling for compensations
430 when damaged by these. For example, the costs to compensate farmers for yield
431 losses due to the 2018 droughts represented €572 Mio. in Germany, Sweden and
432 Poland alone (Bastos et al., 2020).

433 Another burden on ecosystems and society originates from the overuse of
434 agrochemicals, with severe health implications. A pan-European study showed that
435 84% of urine samples collected from adults and children in five countries contained at
436 least two different pesticides, with children being particularly affected (Ottenbros et al.,
437 2023). Among the health impacts, an increased incidence in Parkinson's disease in
438 Europe has been linked to long-term exposure to synthetic pesticides (Paul et al.,
439 2023). The health costs due to nitrogen exposure were estimated at €75-485 bn./year,
440 compared to a net benefit of its usage estimated at €20-80 bn./year at the EU level
441 (Van Grinsven et al., 2013).

442 By contributing to climate change mitigation, and minimising biodiversity loss
443 and pesticide overuse, the measures proposed by the NRR and SUR can have
444 economic benefits that outweigh the costs. It is estimated that restoring 10% of the
445 areas protected under the Habitats Directive to so-called "good condition" within EU

446 territory would cost in total circa €154 billion. The projected benefits of restoring the
447 EU's biodiversity-rich habitats are expected to reach €1,860 billion: a cost-benefit ratio
448 of 1:12 (European Commission, 2022c). Moreover, restoring carbon-rich ecosystems
449 provides significant economic benefits by mitigating climate change damages
450 (Hepburn et al., 2020). For instance, the monetary value of the carbon stock of the
451 seagrass meadows of the Baltic Sea alone was determined to be €231.9 millions (Röhr
452 et al., 2016) and the value of the carbon stock of European forests has been estimated
453 at €1,493/ha (€783-3,468/ha) (Raihan et al., 2021). Beyond monetary value,
454 biodiversity and associated ecosystem services are central to physical and mental
455 wellbeing across a range of environments (Dasgupta, 2021), including urban spaces
456 (Marselle et al., 2021; Methorst et al., 2021), and support intrinsic and relational values
457 (IPBES, 2022; Pascual et al., 2017). As a result, when considering the number of
458 beneficiaries, the NRR and the SUR represent an exceptionally cost-efficient
459 investment rather than a burden for society.

460

461 **7. Ukraine war**

462 A related claim to the 'burden on society' was that one cannot place new policy
463 burdens in a time of war, especially since the war risks increasing food insecurity and
464 destabilising markets. The Russian war on Ukraine indeed generated a shock to food
465 and energy prices and short-term food shortages especially outside the EU. The price
466 for wheat increased from €275/t to circa €400/t in June 2022.

467 However, based on a grain-deal between Russia, Ukraine and Turkey, wheat
468 exports from Ukraine through the Black Sea were maintained in the second half of
469 2022, grain prices dropped to €300/t in January 2023, and the global supply situation
470 stabilized. (Götz & Svanidze, 2023). Despite the termination of the grain-initiative by

471 Russia on July 17th 2023, the situation of the global markets continued to be stable
472 since then. In the medium-term, a tight supply situation for grain, maize and oil-seeds
473 might remain a challenge, but it has no link to biodiversity policies in the EU (Lakner,
474 2023). In fact, *low* prices in the Eastern EU and a reported regional *oversupply* of
475 Ukrainian grain led the EU Commission to *restrict* deliveries of Ukrainian agricultural
476 commodities from March 2023 onwards. In fact, the EU Commission reported a
477 record-high level of exports and imports in 2024 (EC 2025), contradicting the claim
478 that Europe is facing a severe scarcity of commodities due to the war.

479 The war in Ukraine offers no argument to delay environmental legislation,
480 certainly not on the grounds of grain scarcity. As numerous reports demonstrate, such
481 delays are likely to lead to ever-increasing costs of action (Ackerman & Stanton, 2008;
482 Ahmed et al., 2022; OECD, 2019; Sanderson & O'Neill, 2020; Sumaila & Cheung,
483 n.d.). Instead, crises could be wisely used as a window of opportunity, to foster a more
484 rapid transition towards sustainable socio-economic arrangements.

485 Finally, several reports provide more thorough analyses on policy measures
486 that the EU can make in response to the war without compromising its sustainability
487 ambitions (e.g. ARC2020, 2022), with some estimating that a reduction in the demand
488 of both food production and energy for transport and infrastructure development would
489 most effectively address the food scarcity concerns (Creutzig, 2022; Sun et al., 2022).
490 The Green Deal, and the SUR and NRR therein, should therefore be regarded not as
491 a burden in times of war but rather as means to foster transition to sustainable and
492 resilient models of production and consumption, which can reduce dependence on
493 imported energy and agrochemicals, and at the same time ensure that agri-food
494 systems are healthy, fair, self-sufficient and resilient (Iacobaș et al., 2022).

495

496 **8. Renewable energy**

497 Finally, claims were made that the NRR would undermine renewable energy in
498 Europe, particularly biofuel production. It is important to acknowledge the role of forest
499 biomass in reducing fossil fuel use in the short-term in industries heavily reliant on
500 them (Bioenergy Europe, 2020; Cowie et al., 2021). However, the combustion of forest
501 biomass is not carbon-neutral and the climate mitigation potential of this energy source
502 varies widely (Cowie et al., 2021). Under some conditions, it may even emit more CO₂
503 per unit of energy than burning fossil fuels (Schlesinger, 2018).

504 There is an indisputable trade-off in maximising the harvest of wood biomass
505 for bioenergy against restoring and maintaining forests in their natural state for
506 biodiversity, carbon storage and other ecosystem services. This is well illustrated by
507 the case of Finland, where chemical, forest and energy sectors outlined targets for
508 intensified forest biomass use, well above the attainable yield from Finnish forests and
509 over double that of the already high logging level of 2019 (Majava et al., 2022). The
510 increased logging is projected to decrease the carbon sink, jeopardising the 2035
511 climate neutrality goal and posing further risks to already highly endangered
512 biodiversity.

513 The targets on both the restoration of carbon-rich agricultural ecosystems and
514 on renewable energy primarily address the mitigation of climate change. The latest
515 independent assessment demonstrated that bioenergy may play a much smaller role
516 in climate change mitigation than suggested by most earlier scenarios (Merfort et al.,
517 2023). Burning residues and post-consumer wood can have the highest additionality,
518 since this avoids the competing needs for forest biomass, but half of wood burnt in the
519 EU is “primary woody biomass” (about 40% of the EU’s renewable energy; Camia et
520 al., 2021). The practice of burning primary woody biomass is currently economically

521 viable due to considerable public subsidies. It is, therefore, a highly contested tool for
522 climate mitigation in the long term, a social burden, and a high risk for biodiversity and
523 forest ecosystem functions. Achieving the restoration targets under NRR does not
524 preclude use of the restored and remaining forests for multiple products, including that
525 for bioenergy, primarily from the residues and side-streams. Numerous assessments
526 highlight that the best climate change mitigation measures are i) protecting and
527 restoring natural climate sinks, of which forests hold a considerable potential (Mo et
528 al., 2023), and ii) reducing energy demand - especially in transport, buildings and food
529 production, which is possibly even sufficient to cut the EU dependency on imported
530 gas and oil (Creutzig, 2022). Therefore, implementing the NRR is possible on par with
531 restricting burning of primary woody biomass from primary forests and diverting
532 subsidies into zero-emissions renewable energy and energy efficiency measures.

533

534 **Synthesis of claims and scientific evidence**

535 Notably, most claims against the NRR and SUR were linked to agriculture and food
536 production, and based on short-term arguments such as risks of pandemics, military
537 conflicts, and financial crises. While some claims reflected valid concerns, such as
538 potential yield declines and losses of specific job types, most were contrary to the
539 scientific evidence (Table 1). Some claims also misinterpreted the actual nature of
540 measures in the proposals, such as the fact that the NRR focuses primarily on
541 improving the status of protected habitat types rather than the expansion of protected
542 areas. Our overview of scientific evidence highlighted the importance of restoring good
543 ecological conditions of habitats, and in particular, the need to reduce the use of
544 agrochemicals. It suggested that benefits that could be achieved by the NRR and SUR

545 would encompass long-term production capacity of land and marine environments,
546 food security, job creation, innovation, and sustainable production models.

547

548 **xxx Table 1 approximately here xxx**

549

550

551 **The role of scientists in the public debate**

552 **1. Scientists' open letter**

553 The campaign against the NRR and SUR, based on the claims addressed above,
554 originally placed the NRR at risk of rejection, with a 44:44 vote at the environmental
555 committee of the EU's Parliament in June 2023. In response to the misinformation-
556 campaign, scientists (many of whom co-authors of this paper) wrote an open letter in
557 favour of the NRR and SUR delineating the arguments listed above. The letter was
558 signed by 6,000 scientists (Pe'er et al., 2023). Writing the open letter required
559 understanding the two legislative proposals, identifying main claims against these
560 policy proposals, and gathering relevant scientific evidence to address these claims
561 by multi-disciplinary experts, within a short period of time. The open letter was
562 disseminated through scientific networks and its publication was followed by a press
563 conference and invitations for members of Parliament to meet with scientists.

564

565 **2. Adoption of the NRR**

566 The arguments of the open letter provided scientific support to NGOs and businesses,
567 as well as government agencies and parliamentarians making their case in favour of
568 an ambitious NRR and SUR, and voiced by major news outlets (newspapers, radio
569 stations and social media). Overall, public support for the NRR was estimated at 80%

570 in selected EU countries (WWF 2024). The combined actions of NGOs, businesses,
571 concerned policymakers and scientists moved the next Parliamentary vote toward a
572 tight but favourable outcome for the NRR on 12 July 2023. After several rounds of
573 amendments and further negotiations, and with a considerable delay generated by
574 lobby pressures and re-emergence of the same claims (see #9 in Table S1), the NRR
575 was finally approved by the European Council in June 2024, again with a tight result.
576 During this time, numerous scientists published additional supporting letters within
577 their countries, attended science-policy dialogues and events, and delivered
578 supporting evidence in favour of the NRR. Overall, the intense efforts of providing
579 scientific evidence in accessible form and direct interaction with politicians was
580 acknowledged by various politicians and stakeholders as an important contribution to
581 the final approval of the NRR.

582

583 **3. Rejection of the SUR**

584 In 2022, following pressure from the Parliament, the European Commission generated
585 a version of the SUR that was significantly weaker on the environmental targets than
586 the original one. Despite such weakening, the SUR was rejected altogether on 22
587 November 2023, with a majority of 299:207:121 (against: in favour: abstain). In early
588 2024, in response to the farmers' demonstrations, Commissioner von der Leyen
589 announced a full withdrawal of the SUR meaning that the legislative proposal will not
590 be tabled again. This happened despite public support of the SUR signed by over 1.1
591 million EU citizens (see www.savebeesandfarmers.eu/eng), and an open letter signed
592 by hundreds of European scientists, appealing the EU to approve it (Candel 2022).
593 Thus, in this case, the contribution of scientists did not help.

594

595 **Discussion**

596 **Lessons from the different fates of the NRR and SUR**

597 The differing outcomes of negotiations over the NRR and SUR warrant a reflection on
598 possible reasons, as well as the role of science and scientists. In our opinion, three
599 main differences stand out.

600 First, the NRR and SUR differed in terms of consensus level within the society.
601 There is a relative consensus both in society and science for the need to restore
602 nature. In a Eurobarometer survey among >27,000 citizens (Kantar, 2020), 94% of
603 citizens expressed that protecting the environment is important for them; and even
604 among farmers, the EU consultation on “modernising and simplifying the CAP”
605 indicated a majority of farmers supported an improvement in the environmental
606 performance of the CAP (ECORYS, 2017). By contrast, there is less consensus with
607 regards to the feasibility, costs and impacts of reducing agrochemical use. For
608 instance, despite growing evidence (e.g. EEA, 2023), there is still a high level of
609 perceived uncertainty among many citizens about the causal relationship between
610 pesticides and human health impacts. Moreover, implementing alternatives such as
611 Integrated Pest Management requires substantial learning and investments in
612 research, development and extension services (Deguine et al. 2021).

613 Second, the NRR and SUR differ in the degree of voluntary participation. In the
614 NRR, most of the proposed measures are optional for those involved, while in the SUR
615 the measures were obligatory. Moreover, arguments in favour of the SUR were mostly
616 about long-term health benefits for consumers, whereas counter arguments focused
617 on short-term fears regarding food insecurity. For instance, the interruption of supply
618 chains triggered by Covid and the war in Ukraine have influenced the perceptions of
619 food security of European consumers. Moreover, decades of reliance on pesticides

620 have resulted in a high risk-aversion behaviour among many producers (Chèze et al.,
621 2020). This may explain why misinformation was much harder to address in the case
622 of the SUR than in the NRR.

623 Third, the role of industry, and sectors that stood most to lose, differed. If
624 approved, the SUR regulation would have had a direct impact on agrochemical
625 producers, potentially leading toward reduced dependence of farmers on such
626 chemicals. Goulson (2020) highlights the efforts of the agrochemical industry to block
627 initiatives towards the reduction of pesticide use, and Deguine et al. (2021)
628 demonstrates how the agrochemical industry has been shaping the distorted adoption
629 of Integrated Pest Management by lobbying, marketing, and manipulation. As
630 producers of agrochemicals are among the most active and powerful lobbies, pressure
631 on politicians to reject the SUR was likely much higher (Deguine et al., 2020 and
632 references therein). By contrast, the potential impacts of the NRR spread among many
633 sectors, possibly allowing for processes of deliberation and compromise.

634

635 **Global relevance**

636 The debates around the NRR and SUR legislation and environmental policy are not
637 unique to Europe. Globally, land- and sea-use conflicts are worsening and
638 environmental resources are dwindling; while in many parts of the world,
639 environmental legislation and policies are facing increased resistance, pressures for
640 deregulation, or complete cancellation. Likewise, the use of misinformation in
641 environmental debates becomes increasingly common globally. Examples are the use
642 of make-believe controversies and misleading arguments to aid the dismantlement of
643 environmental conservation policies in Brazil (Rajão et al. 2022; Forti et al. 2023),

644 inaccurate claims on the impacts of agrochemical products by those working within
645 the industry, demonstrated for example in a case study in Guatemala (Murray et al.
646 2000), or misleading the public about the causative link between fossil fuel use and
647 climate warming by members of the fossil fuel industry, as e.g. by ExxonMobil in the
648 US (Supran et al., 2023). The Dublin Declaration, a pro-livestock statement on the
649 societal role of livestock without acknowledging health risks and environmental
650 impacts, provides another recent example of a flawed scientific advocacy that shows
651 how selective evidence and unwarranted polarisation can compromise the integrity of
652 academic engagement (Herzon 2024; Krattenmacher et al. 2024). It is increasingly
653 difficult to address the misuse of evidence due to use of sophisticated strategies,
654 including pseudo-scientific claims (e.g. Adams et al., 2023; Farrell et al., 2019; Swire-
655 Thompson & Lazer, 2022) and selective use of evidence by researchers linked to the
656 industry (Krattenmacher et al. 2024). However, as demonstrated by Schmid & Betsch
657 (2019), effective rebuttal strategies of misinformation do work. The case of the NRR
658 provides further evidence on the crucial role of scientists in public debates: by
659 debunking misinformation, highlighting beneficiaries versus losers, and addressing
660 questions of broad societal interests by the scientific community, scientists contributed
661 to the passing of an important regulation that was close to rejection based on
662 misinformation.

663

664 **Toward a constructive dialogue**

665 Societal and political debates are inherent elements of societal transformations, and
666 will become increasingly important in upcoming urgent, cross-sectoral transitions such
667 as those needed towards more environmentally sustainable land and water use
668 practices (Bennett et al., 2019). However, the robust implementation of environmental

669 and social justice principles in the policy process needs to be reliant on using empirical
670 evidence to deliver on policy targets and impacts.

671 Inevitably, any new regulation will either directly or indirectly favour some
672 stakeholders over others: some could take advantage of these regulations, while
673 others may need support in adapting to them. Disparities in the consequences on
674 stakeholders may trigger conflicts, as is known to happen with other sustainability
675 policies, such as transition to low- or zero-carbon economy (Radtke & Scherhauser,
676 2022). Accordingly, it is important to identify wide-ranging and long-term benefits to as
677 many stakeholders as possible, and achieve broad support from society, businesses
678 and policymakers. A constructive dialogue can be guided by highlighting win-wins, or
679 so-called co-benefits (see e.g. Karlsson et al., 2020 for climate). In the case of NRR
680 these include improvements in water quality (Lehtoranta & Louhi, 2021) and protection
681 of cultural heritage (European Commission, 2018).

682 Fostering policy making based on sound scientific evidence requires scientists
683 to be more proactive in public communication (see Garrard et al., 2016, Nelson &
684 Vucetich, 2009, Fuentes, 2024). This requires (a) balancing evidence to distil the
685 emerging best-available evidence; (b) reflecting and communicating complexity,
686 uncertainty and gaps in knowledge in accessible, trustworthy, yet not confusing ways
687 (see also Velado-Alonso 2024); and (c) acknowledging a diversity of opinions while
688 identifying narratives that address societal consensus. Here, one must admit that total
689 certainty is unfeasible in most areas of science, but uncertainty should not be used as
690 an opportunity for delaying action. Importantly, the experience from the NRR case
691 provides another indication that societal and political actors take scientists more
692 seriously when they communicate on the basis of their expertise as reliable knowledge
693 brokers (Nelson & Vucetich, 2009).

694 Universities and research institutes should invest in generating a favourable
695 environment to support science-policy and science-society interactions, in a
696 coordinated and systematic way. This includes extension and outreach faculty
697 members whose job is to aid in science communication and support to local
698 communities, and where the faculty receives credit and recognition in doing so (Buys
699 & Rennekamp 2020). Universities and research institutions should dedicate science-
700 policy coordination and communication staff to facilitate the interactions between
701 scientists and policymakers. As the complexity of environmental problems and the
702 volume of scientific literature grow, meta-analyses, scientific reviews, and other forms
703 of knowledge-synthesis are invaluable. However, yet another step is essential, which
704 is to interpret and communicate science in accessible formats, as done widely in health
705 research, in order to effectively inform public debates and to debunk misinformation
706 (Gerrard et al., 2016). We therefore encourage scientists who work on sustainability
707 topics to be proactive, and to ask for institutional support and training to help avoid
708 communication pitfalls or biases. For policymakers we recommend to use scientific
709 evidence and engage scientists toward much needed, ambitious and robust
710 environmental policies - and in the EU, making use of the 'science-for-policy' interface
711 that was recently initiated by the European Commission exactly for this purpose.

712

713

714 **Conclusion**

715 Sustainable governance of land and sea requires large-scale environmental policies.
716 Synergies and trade-offs will always emerge between nature restoration and economic
717 use of land, sea, and biodiversity. Science and scientists have a pivotal obligation not
718 only to provide evidence through their research, but also to synthesize evidence from

719 diverse findings. When false evidence claims are employed to support the policy
720 interests of lobby groups, scientists should assume the mandate of debunking
721 misleading information and speak up as honest brokers. We can speak with authority
722 when we draw upon our own expertise. To this end we should collaborate across
723 disciplines, communicate complexity and uncertainty, and acknowledge different
724 viewpoints. To address complex societal challenges, both science and science
725 communication are imperative to inform evidence-based policy.

726

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743

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References

- Ackerman, F., & Stanton, E. (2008). *Climate change – the costs of inaction*.
http://frankackerman.com/publications/climatechange/Climate_Change_US_Econocmy.pdf
- Adams, Z., Osman, M., Bechlivanidis, C. and Meder, B., 2023. (Why) is misinformation a problem?. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, p.17456916221141344.
- Ahmed, D. A., Hudgins, E. J., Cuthbert, R. N., Kourantidou, M., Diagne, C., Haubrock, P. J., Leung, B., Liu, C., Leroy, B., Petrovskii, S., Beidas, A., & Courchamp, F. (2022). Managing biological invasions: The cost of inaction. *Biological Invasions*, 24(7), 1927–1946. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-022-02755-0>
- Alliance Environment. (2020). *Evaluation of the impact of the CAP on habitats, landscapes, biodiversity: Final report*. European Commission.
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2762/818843>
- Anastasiou, E., Fountas, S., Voulgaraki, M., Psiroukis, V., Koutsiaras, M., Kriezi, O., Lazarou, E., Vatsanidou, A., Fu, L., Di Bartolo, F. and Barreiro-Hurle, J., 2023. Precision farming technologies for crop protection: A meta-analysis. *Smart Agricultural Technology*, 5, p.100323.
- ARC2020 (2022) *CAP Strategic Plans: Reforming the CAP in wartime* - Project Report. Brussels.
- Barnes, A. E., Davies, J. G., Martay, B., Boersch-Supan, P. H., Harris, S. J., Noble, D. G., Pearce-Higgins, J. W., & Robinson, R. A. (2023). Rare and declining bird species benefit most from designating protected areas for conservation in the UK. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 7(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01927-4>

- Barreiro, H. J., Bogonos, M., Himics, M., Hristov, J., Perez, D. I., Sahoo, A., Salputra, G., Weiss, F., Baldoni, E., & Elleby, C. (2021, July 29). *Modelling environmental and climate ambition in the agricultural sector with the CAPRI model*. JRC Publications Repository. <https://doi.org/10.2760/98160>
- Baquedano, F., Jelliffe, J., Beckman, J., Ivanic, M., Zereyesus, Y. and Johnson, M., 2022. Food security implications for low- and middle- income countries under agricultural input reduction: The case of the European Union's farm to fork and biodiversity strategies. *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 44(4), pp.1942-1954.
- Bastos, A., Ciais, P., Friedlingstein, P., Sitch, S., Pongratz, J., Fan, L., Wigneron, J. P., Weber, U., Reichstein, M., Fu, Z., Anthoni, P., Arneth, A., Haverd, V., Jain, A. K., Joetzjer, E., Knauer, J., Lienert, S., Loughran, T., McGuire, P. C., ... Zaehle, S. (2020). Direct and seasonal legacy effects of the 2018 heat wave and drought on European ecosystem productivity. *Science Advances*, 6(24), eaba2724. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba2724>
- Becker, S., Grajewski, R., & Rehburg, P. (2022). *Where does the CAP money go? : Design and priorities of the draft CAP Strategic Plans 2023-2027*. Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut. <https://doi.org/10.3220/WP1655118238000>
- Beckman, J., Ivanic, M., Jelliffe, J.L. Baquedano, F.G. & Scott, S.G. (2020). *Economic and Food Security Impacts of Agricultural Input Reduction Under the European Union Green Deal's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies*. EB-30, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Economic Research Service
- Beckmann, M., Gerstner, K., Akin- Fajjiye, M., Ceaușu, S., Kambach, S., Kinlock, N. L., Phillips, H. R. P., Verhagen, W., Gurevitch, J., Klotz, S., Newbold, T., Verburg, P. H., Winter, M., & Seppelt, R. (2019). Conventional land- use intensification reduces species richness and increases production: A global meta- analysis. *Global Change Biology*, 25(6), 1941–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14606>
- Bekessy, S.A., Wintle, B.A., Lindenmayer, D.B., Mccarthy, M.A., Colyvan, M., Burgman, M.A. and Possingham, H.P., 2010. The biodiversity bank cannot be a

lending bank. *Conservation Letters*, 3(3), pp.151-158.

<https://conbio.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2010.00110.x>

Bennett, N.J.; Blythe, J.; Cisneros-Montemayor, A.M.; Singh, G.G.; Sumaila, U.R. Just

Transformations to Sustainability. *Sustainability* 2019, 11, 3881

Bethge, S., & Lakner, S. (2023, February 24). Farmers' attitudes toward the future of direct payments: An empirical study from Germany. *GJAE – German Journal of Agricultural Economics*. <https://www.gjae-online.de/articles/farmers-attitudes-toward-the-future-of-direct-payments-an-empirical-study-from-germany/>

Economics. <https://www.gjae-online.de/articles/farmers-attitudes-toward-the-future-of-direct-payments-an-empirical-study-from-germany/>

Bioenergy Europe (2020). Statistical Report 2019 - Biomass Supply.

Björkvik, E., Boonstra, W. J., Hentati-Sundberg, J., & Österblom, H. (2020). Swedish Small-Scale Fisheries in the Baltic Sea: Decline, Diversity and Development. In J. J.

Pascual-Fernández, C. Pita, & M. Bavinck (Eds.), *Small-Scale Fisheries in Europe: Status, Resilience and Governance* (pp. 559–579). Springer International Publishing.

Status, Resilience and Governance (pp. 559–579). Springer International Publishing.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37371-9_27

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37371-9_27

Bohan, D. A., Richter, A., Bane, M., Therond, O., & Pocock, M. J. O. (2022). Farmer-led agroecology for biodiversity with climate change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*,

Trends in Ecology & Evolution,

37(11), 927–930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.07.006>

Bonn, A., Allott, T., Evans, M., Joosten, H. & Stoneman, R. (2016) *Peatland restoration and ecosystem services: Science, policy and practice*. *Ecological Reviews*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

Ecological Reviews. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.

University Press, Cambridge.

Bossard, C., Santin, G., & Guseva Canu, I. (2016). Suicide Among Farmers in France: Occupational Factors and Recent Trends. *Journal of Agromedicine*, 21(4), 310–315.

Journal of Agromedicine, 21(4), 310–315.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1059924X.2016.1211052>

Buchenrieder, G., 2007. *Conceptual framework for analysing structural change in agriculture and rural livelihoods*. Discussion Paper, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Central and Eastern Europe (IAMO) 13, 1–83.

Conceptual framework for analysing structural change in agriculture and rural livelihoods. Discussion Paper, Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Central and Eastern Europe (IAMO) 13, 1–83.

Development in Central and Eastern Europe (IAMO) 13, 1–83.

<http://hdl.handle.net/10419/28462>

- Camia, A., Giuntoli, J., Jonsson., K., Robert, N., Cazzaniga, N., Jasinevičius, G., Avitabile, V., Grassi, G., Barredo Cano, J. I., & Mubareka, S. (2021). *The use of woody biomass for energy production in the EU. JRC122719*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/428400>
- Candel, J. (2022a). EU food-system transition requires innovative policy analysis methods. *Nature Food*, 3(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-022-00518-7>
- Candel, J. (2022b). Scientists call for ambitious Sustainable Use of Pesticides Regulation (Version 4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472705>
- Castle, D., Grass, I., & Westphal, C. (2019). Fruit quantity and quality of strawberries benefit from enhanced pollinator abundance at hedgerows in agricultural landscapes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 275, 14–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.01.003>
- Cavraro, F., Monti, M. A., Caccin, A., Fiori, F., Grati, F., Russo, E., Scarcella, G., Vrdoljak, D., Matić-Skoko, S., & Pranovi, F. (2023). Is the Small-Scale Fishery more sustainable in terms of GHG emissions? A case study analysis from the Central Mediterranean Sea. *Marine Policy*, 148, 105474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105474>.
- Chèze, B., David, M., Martinet, V., (2020). Understanding farmers' reluctance to reduce pesticide use: A choice experiment. *Ecological Economics* 167, 106349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.06.004>
- Convention on Biological Diversity. (2022). *Decision adopted by the conference of the parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity 15/4. Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework*. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>
- Cook, C.N., Mascia, M.B., Schwartz, M.W., Possingham, H.P. and Fuller, R.A., 2013. Achieving conservation science that bridges the knowledge–action boundary. *Conservation Biology*, 27(4), pp.669-678.

- Costa, C., Wollenberg, E., Benitez, M., Newman, R., Gardner, N., & Bellone, F. (2022). Roadmap for achieving net-zero emissions in global food systems by 2050. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 15064. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-18601-1>
- Cowie, A. L., Berndes, G., Bentsen, N. S., Brandão, M., Cherubini, F., Egnell, G., George, B., Gustavsson, L., Hanewinkel, M., Harris, Z. M., Johnsson, F., Junginger, M., Kline, K. L., Koponen, K., Koppejan, J., Kraxner, F., Lamers, P., Majer, S., Marland, E., ... Ximenes, F. A. (2021). Applying a science- based systems perspective to dispel misconceptions about climate effects of forest bioenergy. *GCB Bioenergy*, 13(8), 1210–1231. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12844>
- Creutzig, F. (2022). Fuel crisis: Slash demand in three sectors to protect economies and climate. *Nature*, 606(7914), 460–462. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-01616-z>
- D'Agostino, V. (2018, October 2). *Drought in Europe Summer 2018: Crisis management in an orderly chaos*. Farm Europe. <https://www.farm-europe.eu/blog-en/drought-in-europe-summer-2018-crisis-management-in-an-orderly-chaos/>
- Dainese, M., Martin, E.A., Aizen, M.A., Albrecht, M., Bartomeus, I., Bommarco, R., Carvalheiro, L.G., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Gagic, V., Garibaldi, L.A. and Ghazoul, J. (2019). A global synthesis reveals biodiversity-mediated benefits for crop production. *Science advances*, 5(10), p.eaax0121.
- Dasgupta, P. (2021). *The economics of biodiversity: The Dasgupta Review*. HM Treasury. [https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/962785/The Economics of Biodiversity The Dasgupta Review Full Report.pdf](https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/962785/The_Economics_of_Biodiversity_The_Dasgupta_Review_Full_Report.pdf)
- Deguine, J.-P., Aubertot, J.-N., Flor, R. J., Lescourret, F., Wyckhuys, K. A. G., & Ratnadass, A. (2021). Integrated pest management: Good intentions, hard realities. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 41(3), 38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00689-w>

- Di Lorenzo, M., Guidetti, P., Di Franco, A., Calò, A., & Claudet, J. (2020). Assessing spillover from marine protected areas and its drivers: A meta-analytical approach. *Fish and Fisheries*, 21(5), 906–915. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12469>
- Dixon, S. J., Sear, D. A., Odoni, N. A., Sykes, T., & Lane, S. N. (2016). The effects of river restoration on catchment scale flood risk and flood hydrology: The effects of river restoration on catchment scale flood risk. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 41(7), 997–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3919>
- Dureuil, M., Boerder, K., Burnett, K. A., Froese, R., & Worm, B. (2018). Elevated trawling inside protected areas undermines conservation outcomes in a global fishing hot spot. *Science*, 362(6421), 1403–1407. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau0561>
- ECORYS. (2017). *Modernizing and simplifying the Common Agricultural CAP: Summary of the results of the Public Consultation. Analysis for European Commission, DG for Agriculture & Rural Development.*
- Edgar, G. J., Stuart-Smith, R. D., Willis, T. J., Kininmonth, S., Baker, S. C., Banks, S., Barrett, N. S., Becerro, M. A., Bernard, A. T. F., Berkhout, J., Buxton, C. D., Campbell, S. J., Cooper, A. T., Davey, M., Edgar, S. C., Försterra, G., Galván, D. E., Irigoyen, A. J., Kushner, D. J., ... Thomson, R. J. (2014). Global conservation outcomes depend on marine protected areas with five key features. *Nature*, 506(7487), Article 7487. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13022>
- EEA (European Environmental Agency)(2023) *How pesticides impact human health and ecosystems in Europe.* <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/how-pesticides-impact-human-health/>
- EEAC Network. (2022). *Towards a sustainable food system – a position paper on the framework law.* European Environment and Sustainable Development Advisory Councils Network Foundation. https://eeac.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Towards-a-sustainable-food-system-_-An-EEAC-Network-Position-Paper-PV.pdf
- Euronews (2023) *Nature Restoration Law survives knife-edge vote in the European Parliament amid right-wing backlash* <https://www.euronews.com/my->

[europe/2023/07/12/nature-restoration-law-survives-knife-edge-vote-in-the-european-parliament-amid-right-wing](https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f8ada447-9c99-402c-8bc2-2adb2da27453_en?filename=monitoring-agri-food-trade_jan2025_en.pdf)

European Commission. (2024). Monitoring EU Agri-Food Trade; developments in October 2024. European Commission, DG AGRI News, 24.1.2025

(https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/f8ada447-9c99-402c-8bc2-2adb2da27453_en?filename=monitoring-agri-food-trade_jan2025_en.pdf)

European Commission. (2023). *EU cereal balance sheets, 2005/2006-2021/2022; Data-set by DG Agriculture and Rural Development*. Brussels.

https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/document/download/61c30118-1667-4545-8b5e-b4014bad52c9_en?filename=agri-short-term-outlook-balance-sheets_en.xlsx

European Commission. (2023). Short-Term Outlook: Arable Crops. Spring 2023.

https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/markets/outlook/short-term_en.

European Commission. (2016). *Fitness check of the EU nature legislation (birds and habitats directives) Directive 2009/147/EC of the European parliament and of the council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds and council directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora. Commission staff working document*. European Commission.

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2017-01/swd-2016-472-final_en.pdf

European Commission (2019). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - The European Green Deal, COM/2019/640 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52019DC0640>

European Commission (2020a). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 - Bringing nature back into our lives*, COM/2020/380 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0380>

European Commission (2020b). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – A Farm to Fork Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*, COM/2020/381 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0381>

European Commission. (2021). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All. EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil'*, COM/2021/400 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2021:400:FIN>

European Commission. (2022a). *Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on nature restoration*, COM/2022/304 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0304>

European Commission. (2022b). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the sustainable use of plant protection products and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/2115*, COM/2022/305 final. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0305>

European Commission. (2022c). *Restoring nature: For the benefit of people, nature and the climate*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/439286>

European Commission. (2022d, June 22). *Farm to Fork: New rules to reduce the risk and use of pesticides in the EU* [Text]. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_22_3694

European Commission. (2022e) *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Safeguarding food security and reinforcing the resilience of food systems*. 23.3.2022, COM(2022) 133 final, Brussels, Belgium. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/food-farming->

[fisheries/key_policies/documents/safeguarding-food-security-reinforcing-resilience-food-systems.pdf](#)

European Commission. (2023) Good performance of EU agri-food trade in 2022 despite challenges. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/news/good-performance-eu-agri-food-trade-2022-despite-challenges-2023-04-13_en

European Commission. Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development., Peyraud, J., & MacLeod, M. (2020). *Future of EU livestock: How to contribute to a sustainable agricultural sector? Final report*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2762/3440>

European Environment Agency. (2019a). *Climate change adaptation in the agriculture sector in Europe*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/537176>

European Environment Agency. (2019b). *Natura 2000 Barometer statistics, Report*. European Environmental Agency (EEA).

European Environment Agency. (2020). *State of nature in the EU. Results from reporting under the nature directives 2013-2018* (p. 142). <blob:https://www.eea.europa.eu/92477618-65fa-4c93-a31b-9cf1b03a2900>

European Union. (2023). *Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010*. OJ L 150, 9.6.2023, (pp. 206–247). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023R1115>

Eurostat. (2022). *Farms and farmland in the European Union—Statistics*.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farms_and_farmland_in_the_European_Union_-_statistics

Evans, M., Palmer, K., Aldy, J., Fowlie, M., Kotchen, M. and Levinson, A., (2021). The role of retrospective analysis in an era of deregulation: lessons from the US mercury and air toxics standards. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 15(1), pp.163-168.

- Farrell, J., McConnell, K. and Brulle, R., 2019. Evidence-based strategies to combat scientific misinformation. *Nature climate change*, 9(3), pp.191-195.
- FAO. (2023). *FAOSTAT - Crops and livestock products*.
<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>
- FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO (2021). *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2021*. Rome, Italy
- Fernandes, P. G., Ralph, G. M., Nieto, A., García Criado, M., Vasilakopoulos, P., Maravelias, C. D., Cook, R. M., Pollom, R. A., Kovačić, M., Pollard, D., Farrell, E. D., Florin, A.-B., Polidoro, B. A., Lawson, J. M., Lorance, P., Uiblein, F., Craig, M., Allen, D. J., Fowler, S. L., ... Carpenter, K. E. (2017). Coherent assessments of Europe's marine fishes show regional divergence and megafauna loss. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1(7), Article 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0170>
- Finger, R. (2023). Digital innovations for sustainable and resilient agricultural systems. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, jbad021.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbad021>
- Forti, L.R., Travassos, M.L.D.O., Coronel-Bejarano, D., Miranda, D.F., Souza, D., Sabino, J. and Szabo, J.K. (2023). Posts Supporting Anti-Environmental Policy in Brazil are Shared More on Social Media. *Environmental Management*, 71(6), pp.1188-1198.
- Frank, E.G., 2024. The economic impacts of ecosystem disruptions: Costs from substituting biological pest control. *Science*, 385(6713), p.eadg0344.
- Frid, O., Malamud, S., Di Franco, A., Guidetti, P., Azzurro, E., Claudet, J., Micheli, F., Yahel, R., Sala, E., & Belmaker, J. (2023). Marine protected areas' positive effect on fish biomass persists across the steep climatic gradient of the Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 60(4), 638–649. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14352>
- Froese, R., Winker, H., Coro, G., Demirel, N., Tsikliras, A.C., Dimarchopoulou, D., Scarcella, G., Quaas, M. and Matz-Lück, N. (2018). Status and rebuilding of European fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 93, pp.159-170.

- Fuentes, A. (2024). Scientists as political advocates. *Science*, 385, Issue 6724.
- Garrard, G. E., Fidler, F., Wintle, B. C., Chee, Y. E., & Bekessy, S. A. (2016). Beyond advocacy: making space for conservation scientists in public debate. *Conservation Letters*, 9(3), 208-212.
- Gascuel, D., Bez, N., Forest, A., Guillotreau, P., Laloë, F., Lobry, J., Mahévas, S., Mesnil, B., Rivot, E., Rochette, S., & Trenkel, V. (2011). A future for marine fisheries in Europe (Manifesto of the Association Française d'Halieumétrie). *Fisheries Research*, 109(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2011.02.002>
- Gasparri, N.I., Kuemmerle, T., Meyfroidt, P., Le Polain de Waroux, Y. and Kreft, H., 2016. The emerging soybean production frontier in Southern Africa: conservation challenges and the role of south- south telecouplings. *Conservation Letters*, 9(1), pp.21-31.
- Ghermandi, A., Ding, H., & Nunes, P. A. L. D. (2013). The social dimension of biodiversity policy in the European Union: Valuing the benefits to vulnerable communities. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 33, 196–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2013.06.004>
- Gill, D.A., Mascia, M.B., Ahmadi, G.N., Glew, L., Lester, S.E., Barnes, M., Craigie, I., Darling, E.S., Free, C.M., Geldmann, J. and Holst, S., 2017. Capacity shortfalls hinder the performance of marine protected areas globally. *Nature*, 543(7647), pp.665-669
- Götz, L., & Svanidze, M. (2023). Getreidehandel und Exportbeschränkungen während des Ukrainekrieges. *Wirtschaftsdienst*, 103(13), 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.2478/wd-2023-0065>
- Goulson, D. (2020). Pesticides, corporate Irresponsibility, and the fate of our Planet. *One Earth*, 2(4), 302-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.03.004>
- Greenstreet, S. P. R., Fraser, H. M., & Piet, G. J. (2009). Using MPAs to address regional-scale ecological objectives in the North Sea: Modelling the effects of fishing effort

displacement. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 66(1), 90–100.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn214>

Grorud-Colvert, K., Sullivan-Stack, J., Roberts, C., Constant, V., Horta e Costa, B., Pike, E. P., Kingston, N., Laffoley, D., Sala, E., Claudet, J., Friedlander, A. M., Gill, D. A., Lester, S. E., Day, J. C., Gonçalves, E. J., Ahmadi, G. N., Rand, M., Villagomez, A., Ban, N. C., ... Lubchenco, J. (2021). The MPA Guide: A framework to achieve global goals for the ocean. *Science*, 373(6560), eabf0861.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abf0861>

Gundersen, T., Alinejad, D., Branch, T.Y., Duffy, B., Hewlett, K., Holst, C., Owens, S., Panizza, F., Tellmann, S.M., Van Dijck, J., Baghrmian, M., 2022. A New Dark Age? Truth, Trust, and Environmental Science. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 47, 5–29.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-120920-015909>

Hartley, K. and Vu, M.K., 2020. Fighting fake news in the COVID-19 era: policy insights from an equilibrium model. *Policy sciences*, 53(4), pp.735-758.

Harvey, J.A., Tougeron, K., Gols, R., Heinen, R., Abarca, M., Abram, P.K., Basset, Y., Berg, M., Boggs, C., Brodeur, J. and Cardoso, P. (2023). Scientists' warning on climate change and insects. *Ecological monographs*, 93(1), p.e1553.

Henning, C., Witzke, P., Panknin, L., & Grunenberg, M. (2021). *Ökonomische und Ökologische Auswirkungen des Green Deals in der Agrarwirtschaft. Eine Simulationstudie der E ekte der F2F-Strategie auf Produktion, Handel, Einkommen und Umwelt mit dem CAPRI- Modell*. <https://www.bio-pop.agrarpol.uni-kiel.de/de/f2f-studie/vollversion-der-studie-deutsch>

Hepburn, C., O'Callaghan, B., Stern, N., Stiglitz, J., & Zenghelis, D. (2020). Will COVID-19 fiscal recovery packages accelerate or retard progress on climate change? *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 36(Supplement_1), S359–S381.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/graa015>

Hering, D., Schürings, C., Wenskus, F., Blackstock, K., Borja, A., Birk, S., Bullock, C., Carvalho, L., Bou Dagher Kharrat, M., Lakner, S., Lovrić, N., McGuinness, S.,

Nabuurs, G.-J., Sánchez-Arcilla, A., Settele, J., Pe'er, G. (2023): *Securing success for the Nature Restoration Law*. *Science* 382 (6676), 1248 - 1250.

Herzon I. 2024. What can the Dublin Declaration teach us about credible scientific advocacy? *The Table Debates*, 30 Sep 2024. Available <https://tabledebates.org/essays/what-can-dublin-declaration-teach-us-about-credible-scientific-advocacy>

Holt-Giménez, E., Shattuck, A., Altieri, M., Herren, H., & Gliessman, S. (2012). We already grow enough food for 10 billion people ... and still can't end hunger. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 36(6), 595–598.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10440046.2012.695331>

Iacobuță, G. I., Onbargi, A. F., Bolduc, N., Dzebo, A., Keijzer, N., & Malerba, D. (2022). *The European Green Deal and the war in Ukraine: Addressing crises in the short and long term*. European Think Tanks Group. <https://ettg.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/The-European-Green-Deal-and-the-war-in-Ukraine.pdf>

IPBES. (2018). The IPBES assessment report on land degradation and restoration. Montanarella, L., Scholes, R., and Brainich, A. (eds.). Secretariat of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, Bonn, Germany. 744 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237393>

IPBES. (2019). Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Díaz, J. Settele, E. S. Brondízio E.S., H. T. Ngo, M. Guèze, J. Agard, A. Arneth, P. Balvanera, K. A. Brauman, S. H. M. Butchart, K. M. A. Chan, L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii, J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, G. F. Midgley, P. Miloslavich, Z. Molnár, D. Obura, A. Pfaff, S. Polasky, A. Purvis, J. Razzaque, B. Reyers, R. Roy Chowdhury, Y. J. Shin, I. J. Visseren-Hamakers, K. J. Willis, and C. N. Zayas (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 56 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3553579>

- IPBES. (2022). Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Balvanera P., Pascual U., Christie M., Baptiste B., González-Jiménez D.(eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6522522>
- Issifu, I., Alava, J. J., Lam, V. W. Y., & Sumaila, U. R. (2022). Impact of Ocean Warming, Overfishing and Mercury on European Fisheries: A Risk Assessment and Policy Solution Framework. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2021.770805>
- Jeanneret, P., Lüscher, G., Schneider, M. K., Pointereau, P., Arndorfer, M., Bailey, D., Balázs, K., Báldi, A., Choisis, J.-P., Dennis, P., Diaz, M., Eiter, S., Elek, Z., Fjellstad, W., Frank, T., Friedel, J. K., Geijzendorffer, I. R., Gillingham, P., Gomiero, T., ... Herzog, F. (2021). An increase in food production in Europe could dramatically affect farmland biodiversity. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 2(1), Article 1.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00256-x>
- JRC. (2023). *EU soil observatory and EUSO soil health dashboard. Website by the Joint Research Centre of the European Union, Brussels & Sevilla.*
<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esdacviewer/euso-dashboard/>
- Kantar. (2020). *Attitudes of Europeans towards the Environment (Eurobarometer survey).* European Commission. <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2257>
- Karlsson, M., Alfredsson, E. and Westling, N., 2020. Climate policy co-benefits: a review. *Climate Policy*, 20(3), pp.292-316.
- Kastner, T., Chaudhary, A., Gingrich, S., Marques, A., Persson, U. M., Bidoglio, G., Le Provost, G., & Schwarzmüller, F. (2021). Global agricultural trade and land system sustainability: Implications for ecosystem carbon storage, biodiversity, and human nutrition. *One Earth*, 4(10), 1425–1443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.09.006>

- Krattenmacher, J., Espinosa, R., Sanders, E., Twine, R. and Ripple, W.J. (2024). The Dublin declaration: Gain for the meat industry, loss for science. *Environmental Science & Policy*, p.103922.
- Kurth, T., Rubel, H., Meyer zum Felde, A., Krüger, J.-A., Zielcke, S., Günther, M., & Kemmerling, B. (2019). *Sustainably securing the future of agriculture. Impulses and scenarios for ecological, economic and social sustainability – using agriculture in Germany as an example*. Boston Consulting Group.
<https://www.bcg.com/publications/2020/evaluating-agricultures-environmental-costs>
- Lakner, S. (2023). Auswirkungen des Ukrainekrieges auf die EU-Agrarpolitik. *Wirtschaftsdienst*, 103(13), 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.2478/wd-2023-0066>
- Lakner, S., Klümper, W., & Mensah, K. (2022). *Ukraine-Krieg und globale Lebensmittelversorgung: Auswirkungen und agrarpolitische Handlungsoptionen. Politische Studie im Auftrag von Martin Häusling, MEP und Sarah Wiener, MEP*.
https://www.martin-haeusling.eu/images/STUDIE_Ukraine-Krieg_und_globale_Lebensmittelversorgung_WEB.pdf
- Langer, L., Tripney, J., Gough, D., 2016. *The science of using science: researching the use of research evidence in decision-making*. UCL Institute of Education, EPPI-Centre, London.
- Le Coent, P., Graveline, N., Altamirano, M. A., Arfaoui, N., Benitez-Avila, C., Biffin, T., Calatrava, J., Dartee, K., Douai, A., Gnonlonfin, A., Hérivaux, C., Marchal, R., Moncoulon, D., & Piton, G. (2021). Is-it worth investing in NBS aiming at reducing water risks? Insights from the economic assessment of three European case studies. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 1, 100002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2021.100002>
- Le Provost, G., Schenk, N. V., Penone, C., Thiele, J., Westphal, C., Allan, E., Ayasse, M., Blüthgen, N., Boeddinghaus, R. S., Boesing, A. L., Bolliger, R., Busch, V., Fischer, M., Gossner, M. M., Hölzel, N., Jung, K., Kandeler, E., Klaus, V. H., Kleinebecker, T., ... Manning, P. (2022). The supply of multiple ecosystem services requires

biodiversity across spatial scales. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01918-5>

Lechenet, M., Bretagnolle, V., Bockstaller, C., Boissinot, F., Petit, M.-S., et al. (2014)

Reconciling pesticide reduction with economic and environmental sustainability in arable farming. *PLoS ONE* 9(6): e97922. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0097922

Lechenet, M., Dessaint, F., Py, G., Makowski, D., & Munier-Jolain, N. (2017). Reducing pesticide use while preserving crop productivity and profitability on arable farms.

Nature Plants, 3(3), 17008. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nplants.2017.8>

Lécuyer, L., Alard, D., Calla, S., Coolsaet, B., Fickel, T., Heinsoo, K., Henle, K., Herzon, I.,

Hodgson, I., Quétier, F., McCracken, D., McMahon, B. J., Melts, I., Sands, D.,

Skrimizea, E., Watt, A., White, R., & Young, J. (2021). Conflicts between agriculture and biodiversity conservation in Europe: Looking to the future by learning from the past. In *Advances in Ecological Research* (Vol. 65, pp. 3–56). Elsevier.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2021.10.005>

Lehtoranta, V., & Louhi, P. (2021). Does conservation in Natura 2000 areas promote water quality improvement? Findings from a contingent valuation study on environmental

benefits and residents' preferences. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 124, 226–234.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.06.019>

Lenton, T. M., Rockström, J., Gaffney, O., Rahmstorf, S., Richardson, K., Steffen, W., &

Schellnhuber, H. J. (2019). Climate tipping points—Too risky to bet against. *Nature*,

575(7784), 592–595. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-019-03595-0>

Liquete, C., Prakash, S., Addamo, A., Assouline, M., Barredo Cano, J. I., Bosco, S., De

Jesus Cardoso, A., Da Silva Catarino, R., Czucz, B., Druon, J., Fellmann, T.,

Gliottone, I., Guerrero Fernandez, I., Montero Castaño, A., Panagos, P., Paracchini,

M., Pardo Valle, A., Polce, C., Rega, C., ... Vasilakopoulos, P. (2022). *Scientific*

evidence showing the impacts of nature restoration actions on food productivity, EUR

31137 EN, JRC129725. Publications Office of the European Union.

<https://doi.org/10.2760/3032>

- Majava, A., Vadén, T., Toivanen, T., Järvensivu, P., Lähde, V., & Eronen, J. T. (2022). Sectoral low-carbon roadmaps and the role of forest biomass in Finland's carbon neutrality 2035 target. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 41, 100836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2022.100836>
- Marselle, M. R., Lindley, S. J., Cook, P. A., & Bonn, A. (2021). Biodiversity and health in the urban environment. *Current Environmental Health Reports*, 8(2), 146–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-021-00313-9>
- Mehl, D. (2017). 25 Jahre Fließgewässerrenaturierung an der mecklenburgischen Nebel: Auswirkungen auf den ökologischen Zustand und auf regulative Ökosystemleistungen [PDF]. *Hydrologie und Wasserbewirtschaftung / BfG – Jahrgang: 62.2018*, 1ISSN 1439. https://doi.org/10.5675/HYWA_2018,1_1
- Merfort, L., Bauer, N., Humpenöder, F., Klein, D., Streffler, J., Popp, A., Luderer, G., & Kriegler, E. (2023). Bioenergy-induced land-use-change emissions with sectorally fragmented policies. *Nature Climate Change*, 13(7), 685–692. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-023-01697-2>
- Methorst, J., Rehdanz, K., Mueller, T., Hansjürgens, B., Bonn, A., & Böhning-Gaese, K. (2021). The importance of species diversity for human well-being in Europe. *Ecological Economics*, 181, 106917. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106917>
- Mo, L., Zohner, C.M., Reich, P.B., Liang, J., De Miguel, S., Nabuurs, G.J., Renner, S.S., van den Hoogen, J., Araza, A., Herold, M. and Mirzaghali, L., 2023. Integrated global assessment of the natural forest carbon potential. *Nature*, 624(7990), pp.92-101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06723-z>
- Möhring, N., Ingold, K., Kudsk, P., Martin-Laurent, F., Niggli, U., Siegrist, M., Studer, B., Walter, A., & Finger, R. (2020). Pathways for advancing pesticide policies. *Nature Food*, 1(9), 535–540. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-020-00141-4>
- Murray D.L., Taylor, P.L. (2000) Claim no easy victories: evaluating the pesticide industry's global safe use campaign. *World Development*, 28:1735–1749. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(00\)00059-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(00)00059-0)

Gafney, A. (2025) Science Data May Soon Disappear from Government Websites. New York Times, 21.3.2025.

<https://www.nytimes.com/2025/03/21/climate/government-websites-climate-environment-data.html>

OECD. (2019). *Biodiversity: Finance and the Economic and Business Case for Action*.

OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/a3147942-en>

Oppla. (2023). *EU repository of nature-based solutions*. Oppla. <https://oppla.eu/>

Ottenbros, I., Lebrecht, E., Huber, C., Lommen, A., Antignac, J.-P., Čupr, P., Šulc, L., Mikeš, O., Szigeti, T., Középesy, S., Martinsone, I., Martinsone, Z., Akulova, L., Pardo, O., Fernández, S. F., Coscollá, C., Pedraza-Díaz, S., Krauss, M., Debrauwer, L., ...

Vlaanderen, J. (2023). Assessment of exposure to pesticide mixtures in five European countries by a harmonized urinary suspect screening approach.

International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health, 248, 114105.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2022.114105>

Parfitt, J., Barthel, M., & Macnaughton, S. (2010). Food waste within food supply chains: Quantification and potential for change to 2050. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 365(1554), 3065–3081.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0126>

Pascual, U., Balvanera, P., Díaz, S., Pataki, G., Roth, E., Stenseke, M., Watson, R. T., Başak Dessane, E., Islar, M., Kelemen, E., Maris, V., Quaas, M., Subramanian, S. M., Wittmer, H., Adlan, A., Ahn, S., Al-Hafedh, Y. S., Amankwah, E., Asah, S. T., ...

Yagi, N. (2017). Valuing nature's contributions to people: The IPBES approach. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 26–27, 7–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2016.12.006>

Paul, K. C., Krolewski, R. C., Lucumi Moreno, E., Blank, J., Holton, K. M., Ahfeldt, T., Furlong, M., Yu, Y., Cockburn, M., Thompson, L. K., Kreymerman, A., Ricci-Blair, E. M., Li, Y. J., Patel, H. B., Lee, R. T., Bronstein, J., Rubin, L. L., Khurana, V., & Ritz, B. (2023). A pesticide and iPSC dopaminergic neuron screen identifies and classifies

Parkinson-relevant pesticides. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 2803.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38215-z>

Pe'er, G., Birkenstock, M., Lakner, S., & Röder, N. (2021). *The Common Agricultural Policy post-2020: Views and recommendations from scientists to improve performance for biodiversity. Volume 2 - Annexes* (Working Paper No. 175-Volume 2). Thünen Working Paper. <https://doi.org/10.3220/WP1620647428000>

Pe'er, G., Bonn, A., Bruelheide, H., Dieker, P., Eisenhauer, N., Feindt, P. H., Hagedorn, G., Hansjürgens, B., Herzon, I., Lomba, Â., Marquard, E., Moreira, F., Nitsch, H., Oppermann, R., Perino, A., Röder, N., Schleyer, C., Schindler, S., Wolf, C., ... Lakner, S. (2020). Action needed for the EU Common Agricultural Policy to address sustainability challenges. *People and Nature*, 2(2), 305–316. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10080>

Pe'er, G., Finn, J. A., Díaz, M., Birkenstock, M., Lakner, S., Röder, N., Kazakova, Y., Šumrada, T., Bezák, P., Concepción, E. D., Dänhardt, J., Morales, M. B., Rac, I., Špulerová, J., Schindler, S., Stavrínides, M., Targetti, S., Viaggi, D., Vogiatzakis, I. N., & Guyomard, H. (2022). How can the European Common Agricultural Policy help halt biodiversity loss? Recommendations by over 300 experts. *Conservation Letters*, 15(6). <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12901>

Pe'er, G., Kachler, J., Herzon, I., Hering, D., Arponen, A. ... & Bonn, A. (2023). *Scientists support the EU's Green Deal and reject the unjustified argumentation against the Sustainable Use Regulation and the Nature Restoration*. Zenodo, 7.7.2023: <https://zenodo.org/records/8128624>

Pe'er, G., Zingrebe, Y., Moreira, F., Sirami, C., Schindler, S., Müller, R., Bontzorlos, V., Clough, D., Bezák, P., Bonn, A., Hansjürgens, B., Lomba, A., Möckel, S., Passoni, G., Schleyer, C., Schmidt, J., & Lakner, S. (2019). A greener path for the EU Common Agricultural Policy. *Science*, 365(6452), 449–451. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax3146>

- Pendleton, L. H., Ahmadiya, G. N., Browman, H. I., Thurstan, R. H., Kaplan, D. M., & Bartolino, V. (2018). Debating the effectiveness of marine protected areas. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 75(3), 1156–1159. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsx154>
- Perry, A. L., Blanco, J., García, S., & Fournier, N. (2022). Extensive Use of Habitat-Damaging Fishing Gears Inside Habitat-Protecting Marine Protected Areas. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2022.811926>
- Persson, L., Carney Almroth, B. M., Collins, C. D., Cornell, S., de Wit, C. A., Diamond, M. L., Fantke, P., Hassellöv, M., MacLeod, M., Ryberg, M. W., Søgaard Jørgensen, P., Villarrubia-Gómez, P., Wang, Z., & Hauschild, M. Z. (2022). Outside the Safe Operating Space of the Planetary Boundary for Novel Entities. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 56(3), 1510–1521. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04158>
- Pesticide Action Network Europe. (2022). *Forbidden fruit* (p. 51). https://www.pan-europe.info/sites/pan-europe.info/files/public/resources/reports/ForbiddenFruit_01.pdf
- Petit, S., & Landis, D. A. (2023). Landscape-scale management for biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 347, 108370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108370>
- Pielke Jr, R.A., 2007. *The honest broker: making sense of science in policy and politics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Pörtner, H.-O., Scholes, B., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneth, A., Bai, X., Barnes, D., Burrows, M., Chan, L., Cheung, W. L. (William), Diamond, S., Donatti, C., Duarte, C., Eisenhauer, N., Foden, W., Gasalla, M. A., Handa, C., Hickler, T., Hoegh-Guldberg, O., ... Ngo, H. (2021). *Scientific outcome of the IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop on biodiversity and climate change*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4659159>
- Princé, K., Rouveyrol, P., Pellissier, V., Touroult, J., & Jiguet, F. (2021). Long-term effectiveness of Natura 2000 network to protect biodiversity: A hint of optimism for common birds. *Biological Conservation*, 253, 108871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108871>

- Pywell, R. F., Heard, M. S., Woodcock, B. A., Hinsley, S., Ridding, L., Nowakowski, M., & Bullock, J. M. (2015). Wildlife-friendly farming increases crop yield: Evidence for ecological intensification. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282(1816), 20151740. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2015.1740>
- Radtke, J. and Scherhauser, P., 2022. A social science perspective on conflicts in the energy transition: An introduction to the special issue. *Utilities Policy*, 78, p.101396.
- Raihan, A., Ara Begum, R., & Mohd Said, M. N. (2021). A meta-analysis of the economic value of forest carbon stock. *Malaysian Journal of Society and Space*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.17576/geo-2021-1704-22>
- Rajão, R., Nobre, A.D., Cunha, E.L., Duarte, T.R., Marcolino, C., Soares-Filho, B., Sparovek, G., Rodrigues, R.R., Valera, C., Bustamante, M. and Nobre, C. (2022). The risk of fake controversies for Brazilian environmental policies. *Biological conservation*, 266, 109447.
- Rajmis, S., Karpinski, I., Pohl, J.-P., Herrmann, M., & Kehlenbeck, H. (2022). Economic potential of site-specific pesticide application scenarios with direct injection and automatic application assistant in northern Germany. *Precision Agriculture*, 23(6), 2063–2088. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11119-022-09888-1>
- Rakovec, O., Samaniego, L., Hari, V., Markonis, Y., Moravec, V., Thober, S., Hanel, M., & Kumar, R. (2022). The 2018–2020 multi-year drought sets a new benchmark in Europe. *Earth's Future*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EF002394>
- Reganold, J. P., & Wachter, J. M. (2016). Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. *Nature Plants*, 2(2), 15221. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nplants.2015.221>
- Rigal, S., Dakos, V., Alonso, H., Auniņš, A., Benkő, Z., Brotons, L., Chodkiewicz, T., Chylarecki, P., de Carli, E., del Moral, J. C., Domşa, C., Escandell, V., Fontaine, B., Foppen, R., Gregory, R., Harris, S., Herrando, S., Husby, M., Ieronymidou, C., ... Devictor, V. (2023). Farmland practices are driving bird population decline across Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(21), e2216573120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2216573120>

- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., ... & Rockström, J. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.
- Ritchie, H., Reay, D. S., & Higgins, P. (2018). Beyond calories: A holistic assessment of the global food system. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 2. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2018.00057>
- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S., Lambin, E., Lenton, T. M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H. J., Nykvist, B., de Wit, C. A., Hughes, T., van der Leeuw, S., Rodhe, H., Sörlin, S., Snyder, P. K., Costanza, R., Svedin, U., ... Foley, J. (2009). Planetary Boundaries: Exploring the Safe Operating Space for Humanity. *Ecology and Society*, 14(2). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26268316>
- Röhr, M. E., Boström, C., Canal-Vergés, P., & Holmer, M. (2016). Blue carbon stocks in Baltic Sea eelgrass (*Zostera marina*) meadows. *Biogeosciences*, 13(22), 6139–6153. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-13-6139-2016>
- Röös, E., Bajželj, B., Smith, P., Patel, M., Little, D., & Garnett, T. (2017). Protein futures for Western Europe: Potential land use and climate impacts in 2050. *Regional Environmental Change*, 17(2), 367–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-016-1013-4>
- Röös, E., Mayer, A., Muller, A., Kalt, G., Ferguson, S., Erb, K.H., Hart, R., Matej, S., Kaufmann, L., Pfeifer, C. and Frehner, A. (2022). Agroecological practices in combination with healthy diets can help meet EU food system policy targets. *Science of The Total Environment*, 847, p.157612.
- Ruggiero, P.G., Pfaff, A., Nichols, E., Rosa, M. and Metzger, J.P., 2021. Election cycles affect deforestation within Brazil's Atlantic Forest. *Conservation Letters*, 14(5), p.e12818.
- Sala, E., & Giakoumi, S. (2018). No-take marine reserves are the most effective protected areas in the ocean. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 75(3), 1166–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsx059>

- Samet, J.M. & Burke, T.A. (2020). Deregulation and the assault on science and the environment. *Annual review of public health*, 41, pp.347-361.
- Sanderson, B. M., & O'Neill, B. C. (2020). Assessing the costs of historical inaction on climate change. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-66275-4>
- Schlesinger, W. H. (2018). Are wood pellets a green fuel? *Science*, 359(6382), 1328–1329. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat2305>
- Schmid, P., & Betsch, C. (2019) Effective strategies for rebutting science denialism in public discussions. *Nat. Human Behaviour* 3, 931–939. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0632-4>
- Schmidt, T., Schneider, F., Leverenz, D., & Hafner, G. (2019). *Lebensmittelabfälle in Deutschland – Baseline 2015* (No. 71; Thünen Report, p. 109). Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut. <https://doi.org/10.3220/REP1563519883000>
- Schneider, K., Barreiro-Hurle, J. and Rodriguez-Cerezo, E., 2023. Pesticide reduction amidst food and feed security concerns in Europe. *Nature Food*, 4(9), pp.746-750.
- Schneider, M. K., Lüscher, G., Jeanneret, P., Arndorfer, M., Ammari, Y., Bailey, D., Balázs, K., Báldi, A., Choisis, J.-P., Dennis, P., Eiter, S., Fjellstad, W., Fraser, M. D., Frank, T., Friedel, J. K., Garchi, S., Geijzendorffer, I. R., Gomiero, T., Gonzalez-Bornay, G., ... Herzog, F. (2014). Gains to species diversity in organically farmed fields are not propagated at the farm level. *Nature Communications*, 5(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms5151>
- Scown, M. W., Brady, M. V., & Nicholas, K. A. (2020). Billions in Misspent EU Agricultural Subsidies Could Support the Sustainable Development Goals. *One Earth*, 3(2), 237–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.07.011>
- Seppelt, R., Arndt, C., Beckmann, M., Martin, E. A., & Hertel, T. W. (2020). Deciphering the biodiversity–production mutualism in the global food security debate. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 35(11), 1011–1020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2020.06.012>

- Shepon, A., Eshel, G., Noor, E., & Milo, R. (2018). The opportunity cost of animal based diets exceeds all food losses. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(15), 3804–3809. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1713820115>
- Silva, V., et al., 2019, Pesticide residues in European agricultural soils — a hidden reality unfolded. *Science of the Total Environment* 653, 1532-1545. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.441.
- Sotirov, M. (2017). *Natura 2000 and forests: Assessing the state of implementation and effectiveness. What Science Can Tell Us 7*. European Forest Institute.
- Stankus, A. (2021). *State of world aquaculture 2020 and regional reviews: FAO webinar series - ProQuest*. 63, 17–18.
- Steadman, D. (2021). Towards ecological and social impact through collaborative governance of a seascape of marine protected areas in Honduras. *Oryx*, 55(4), 507–518. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0030605320001155>
- Steadman, D., Thomas, J.B., Villanueva, V.R., Lewis, F., Pauly, D., Deng Palomares, M.L., Bailly, N., Levine, M., Viridin, J. and Roccliffe, S., (2021). New perspectives on an old fishing practice: Scale, context and impacts of bottom trawling. *Our Shared Seas*, Report, 44.
- Sumaila, U. R., & Cheung, W. W. L. (n.d.). *Cost of Adapting Fisheries to Climate Change*.
- Sun, Z., Scherer, L., Zhang, Q., & Behrens, P. (2022). Adoption of plant-based diets across Europe can improve food resilience against the Russia–Ukraine conflict. *Nature Food*, 3(11), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-022-00634-4>
- Supran, G., Rahmstorf, S., Orekes, N. (2023) Assessing ExxonMobil's global warming projections. *Science*, 379, eabk0063. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abk0063>
- Suuronen, P., Jounela, P., & Tschernij, V. (2010). Fishermen responses on marine protected areas in the Baltic cod fishery. *Marine Policy*, 34(2), 237–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2009.07.001>

- Swire-Thompson, B. & Lazer, D., 2022. Reducing health misinformation in science: a call to arms. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 700(1), pp.124-135.
- Tanneberger, F., Appulo, L., Ewert, S., Lakner, S., Ó Brolcháin, N., Peters, J. & Wichtmann, W. (2021) The power of nature- based solutions: how peatlands can help us to achieve key EU sustainability objectives. *Advanced Sustainable Systems*, 5, 2000146.
- Temmink, R. J. M., Robroek, B. J. M., van Dijk, G., Koks, A. H. W., Käärmelahti, S. A., Barthelmes, A., Wassen, M. J., Ziegler, R., Steele, M. N., Giesen, W., Joosten, H., Fritz, C., Lamers, L. P. M., & Smolders, A. J. P. (2023). Wetscapes: Restoring and maintaining peatland landscapes for sustainable futures. *Ambio*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01875-8>
- Tostado, L., & Bollmohr, S. (2022). *Pesticide atlas. Facts and figures about toxic chemical in agriculture* (2nd ed.). Heinrich Böll Stiftung.
https://eu.boell.org/sites/default/files/2023-04/pesticideatlas2022_ii_web_20230331.pdf
- Trenczek, J., Lühr, O., Eiserbeck, L., Sandhövel, M., & Ibens, D. (2022). *Projektbericht „Kosten durch Klimawandelfolgen“. Schäden der Dürre- und Hitzeextreme 2018 und 2019. Eine ex-post-Analyse.*
- Tscharntke, T., Clough, Y., Wanger, T. C., Jackson, L., Motzke, I., Perfecto, I., Vandermeer, J., & Whitbread, A. (2012). Global food security, biodiversity conservation and the future of agricultural intensification. *Biological Conservation*, 151(1), 53–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2012.01.068>
- Turkelboom, F., Demeyer, R., Vranken, L., De Becker, P., Raymaekers, F., & De Smet, L. (2021). How does a nature-based solution for flood control compare to a technical solution? Case study evidence from Belgium. *Ambio*, 50(8), 1431–1445.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01548-4>

United Nations (2015) Paris Agreement.

https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/english_paris_agreement.pdf

United Nations (2022) Convention on Biological Diversity. Kunming-Montreal Global

Biodiversity Framework. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-15/cop-15-dec-04-en.pdf>

Van Grinsven, H. J. M., Holland, M., Jacobsen, B. H., Klimont, Z., Sutton, M. a., & Jaap Willems, W. (2013). Costs and benefits of nitrogen for Europe and implications for mitigation. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 47(8), 3571–3579.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/es303804g>

Vandeplass, A., Vanyolos, I., Vigani, M., & Vogel, L. (2022). *The Possible Implications of the Green Transition for the EU Labour Market* (Discussion Paper 176). European Commission.

Vaughan, D. (2017). Fishing effort displacement and the consequences of implementing Marine Protected Area management – An English perspective. *Marine Policy*, 84, 228–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2017.07.007>

Veerman, C., Pinto Correia, T., Bastioli, C., Biro, B., Bouma, J. and Cienciela, E., (2020). *Caring for soil is caring for life*. EU Soil Health and Food Mission Board: Brussels, Belgium.

Velado-Alonso, E., Kleijn, D., & Bartomeus, I. (2024). Reassessing science communication for effective farmland biodiversity conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 39(6), 537-547.

Vona, F. (2019). Job losses and political acceptability of climate policies: Why the ‘job-killing’ argument is so persistent and how to overturn it. *Climate Policy*, 19(4), 524–532.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2018.1532871>

Wachter-Karpfinger, M. and Wytrzens, H.K., 2024. Beyond the preservation of agricultural land—Identifying Austrian farmers’ farming-related interests in local spatial planning. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 105, p.103170.

Westhoek, H., Lesschen, J. P., Rood, T., Wagner, S., De Marco, A., Murphy-Bokern, D., Leip, A., van Grinsven, H., Sutton, M. A., & Oenema, O. (2014). Food choices, health and environment: Effects of cutting Europe's meat and dairy intake. *Global Environmental Change*, 26, 196–205.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.02.004>

Wezel, A., Casagrande, M., Celette, F., Vian, JF., Ferrer, A., Peigné, J. (2014) Agroecological practices for sustainable agriculture. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 34(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-013-0180-7>

Wikipedia, 2025. 2025 United States government online resource removals.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2025_United_States_government_online_resource_removals

WWF, 2024. Citizens' perceptions on nature and biodiversity in the EU. Survey Results. Available <https://wwfeu.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/citizens-survey-nature-biodiversity-NRR-eu.pdf>. Last accessed 03.12.2024.

Yang, J., Ward, M.D. and Kahr, B., 2017. Abuse of Rachel Carson and misuse of DDT science in the service of environmental deregulation. *Angewandte Chemie*, 129(34), 10158-10164.

Zinngrebe, Y., Berger, J., Bunn, C., Felipe-Lucia, M. R., Graßnick, N., Kastner, T., ... & Lakner, S. (2024). Prioritizing partners and products for the sustainability of the EU's agri-food trade. *One Earth*, 7(4), 674-686.

Table 1: Synthesis of the claims against the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) and Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR) and key elements of the scientific analysis. For concrete examples of the claims see Supporting Information Table S1.

Claim	Scientific analysis
1. NRR will take 10% land out of production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Common Agricultural Policy already requires 3% of non-productive areas, and eco-schemes support farmers up to 7% - Land is already being abandoned in marginal regions - An adequate spatial strategy would decrease land abandonment
2. SUR will decrease yield	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decreasing pesticide use without changing other practices may result in up to 30% yield loss - Yield is negatively impacted by soil degradation, climate change and biodiversity loss - Combining a decrease in pesticide use with agroecological practices is necessary to maintain yields
3. NRR and SUR will increase food insecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food insecurity depends on food production, accessibility, diet and waste - EU primarily exports animal products and imports feed - Reducing animal production and overconsumption, food waste and biofuel production is key to increase food security
4. NRR will decrease fishing activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing restrictions would decrease fishing activities within Marine Protected Areas - Fisheries are mainly affected by unsustainable fishing and climate change - Restoring Marine Protected Areas would enhance yield of neighbouring fisheries
5. NRR and SUR will decrease incomes and kill jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The farm to fork strategy may result in loss of jobs and farm income - Jobs are already decreasing despite Common Agricultural Policy investments - NRR and SUR can generate jobs
6. NRR and SUR will place a burden on society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restoring nature in protected areas would cost a total of €154 billion but the estimated benefits are at €1,860, i.e., a 12:1 ratio of benefits to costs - Climate change and pesticide overuse are a burden on society impacting health and extreme weather conditions
7. NRR and SUR are too risky in time of war	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - War generated an increase in food and energy prices in 2022 - Markets have rapidly stabilised in 2023 - Reducing food demand and dependencies to energy imports is key to increase resilience
8. NRR undermines renewable energy targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are trade-offs between increasing forest biomass harvest and other uses/restoration targets - Burning biomass produces emissions and is highly contested for climate change mitigation - NRR could restore natural carbon sinks and mitigate climate change